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How To Build a VR Headset

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It's only those who do nothing that
make no mistakes, I suppose.

Joseph Conrad

Abstract

Virtual Reality is now an established product used across various fields, including education, construction, and research. This work presents a modular 3D-printable VR headset that focuses on hardware customizability and software adaptability. The design includes adjustable interpupillary distance (IPD) and display-to-lens distance, which allows the headset to be configured for different users. To ensure broad compatibility, the system integrates with the OpenXR interface, runs on Windows, and supports different tracking systems. The hardware can be reproduced using 3D printing, making the headset accessible and adaptable for individual requirements.

Through five iterations, each introducing certain features, the final design was developed. The headset follows a modular assembly approach, allowing individual components to be exchanged and upgraded, adding a layer of customization to the overall system. This enables the replacement of lenses, displays, and tracking hardware without redesigning the complete headset. Additionally, Monado, an open-source OpenXR runtime, was adapted with a custom driver developed for this project.

The goal of this work is to provide a foundation for creating a virtual reality headset that can be further adapted and expanded for different use cases. Therefore, an instruction on how to build the headset is provided.

Kurzfassung

Virtual Reality ist mittlerweile ein etabliertes Produkt, das in verschiedenen Bereichen wie Bildung, Bauwesen und Forschung eingesetzt wird. Diese Arbeit präsentiert ein modulares, 3D-druckbares VR-Headset, dessen Schwerpunkt auf der Anpassbarkeit der Hardware und der Software liegt. Das Design umfasst eine einstellbare Pupillendistanz (IPD) und einen einstellbaren Abstand zwischen Display und Linse, wodurch das Headset für verschiedene Benutzer konfiguriert werden kann. Um eine breite Kompatibilität zu gewährleisten, ist das System in die OpenXR-Schnittstelle integriert, läuft unter Windows und unterstützt verschiedene Tracking-Systeme. Die Hardware kann mittels 3D-Druck reproduziert werden, wodurch das Headset zugänglich und an individuelle Anforderungen anpassbar ist.

In fünf Iterationen, in denen jeweils bestimmte Funktionen eingeführt wurden, wurde das endgültige Design entwickelt. Das Headset folgt einem modularen Aufbau, sodass einzelne Komponenten ausgetauscht und aufgerüstet werden können, was dem Gesamtsystem eine zusätzliche Ebene der Anpassbarkeit verleiht. Dadurch können Linsen, Displays und Tracking-Hardware ausgetauscht werden, ohne das gesamte Headset neu zu konstruieren. Zusätzlich wurde Monado, eine Open-Source-OpenXR-Laufzeitumgebung, mit einem speziell für dieses Projekt entwickelten Treiber angepasst.

Das Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, eine Grundlage für die Entwicklung eines Virtual-Reality-Headsets zu schaffen, das für verschiedene Anwendungsfälle weiter angepasst und erweitert werden kann. Daher wird eine Anleitung zum Bau des Headsets bereitgestellt.

Affidavit

I declare that I have authored this thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources/resources, and that I have explicitly indicated all material which has been quoted either literally or by content from the sources used.

The text document uploaded to TUGRAZonline is identical to the present master's thesis dissertation.

Date

Signature

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In today's world, virtual reality (VR) has established itself in multiple fields. An example is architecture. Architects can now create customized 3D experiences to show their clients what their future homes will look and feel like. This leads to a better decision-making process and helps avoid costly changes later on.

In the industry, VR can be used to train workers through interactive courses. This is especially valuable for employees who operate in unsafe environments, as they can learn proper workflows without being exposed to real danger. The same applies to the military. Soldiers can be placed in realistic training scenarios to improve decision-making under stress. Flight simulations help pilots practice maneuvering skills without risk. Mistakes can be made and learned without the risk of consequences.

In the medical field, students can interact with the human body. They can explore every muscle and organ from all angles, which helps them to improve their understanding. Seeing the body in its actual size also provides a better sense of scale, something that is difficult to grasp in textbooks [1].

As seen in these examples, VR has a broad user base with different needs and expectations. Unfortunately, consumer-grade headsets often do not offer the flexibility required for specific use cases. Ecosystems like those of the Oculus headsets are closed source and do not allow any modification of their codebase or access to internal drivers. In addition, these devices are fully sealed and not designed for disassembly, making it difficult or even impossible to replace or upgrade components.

Whether the goal is to swap out the optical system or access deeper software layers to enable driver-level functionality, the limiting factor remains the same: Commercially available headsets are typically locked into fixed hardware and software configurations. Although open standards like OpenXR simplify software development for VR applications, open and modular VR hardware remains rare.

An open system could improve research in multiple fields by providing a foundation on which tracking systems can be freely swapped and integrated. In industrial environments, custom VR headsets could be 3D printed and adapted to fit the needs of niche scenarios.

Education could benefit from custom headset optics tailored to each individual while saving costs by reusing other shared components of the headset.

The goal of this thesis is to design and implement a foundation for a modular VR device. The system should provide enough flexibility in its hardware to accommodate a wide range of use cases. The headset is designed to follow a modular approach, allowing components to be easily replaced, upgraded, or adjusted as needed. Additionally, the software solution should be fully open-source and available for modification, enabling developers and researchers to adapt it to their needs.

The development process is divided into two main parts: hardware and software. The hardware is developed iteratively, starting with a non-functional cardboard prototype, and evolves into a fully 3D-printed, screw-assembled version featuring two adjustment mechanisms. On the software side, an initial prototype is created to test the feasibility of a custom implementation. Later on, an OpenXR framework is introduced to broaden the range of use and also to be compatible with already existing software. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- Designing and iteratively developing a customizable, 3D printable VR headset with modular and adjustable components
- Developing a new device driver for the Monado project to enable custom headset integration through OpenXR
- Creating a Windows-compatible version of the tracking system for Monado using RealSense and a SLAM backend
- Providing a guide on how to compile the custom driver into Monado

With these contributions, the basis for a working custom VR system is set. This enables other people to work on an existing solution and not on a headset from the ground up.

The following chapters provide a full overview of the project. Chapter 2 discusses related work on VR hardware, tracking systems, and open standards. Chapter 3 explains the iterative development process of the hardware, including a reflection on the advantages and limitations. Chapter 4 focuses on software integration, starting from a naive initial approach and leading to a fully functional OpenXR-compatible system using Monado, followed by a discussion. Finally, Chapter 5 summarizes the complete system and outlines possible future improvements.

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In this section, related projects and technologies in the field of Virtual Reality are discussed. This includes the use of standardization for cross-application compatibility, concerns regarding the handling of private data, the customizability of headsets, and tracking technologies in Virtual Reality (VR) headsets.

The use of VR has increased significantly over the past few years. However, research into this technology dates back to 1968. Ivan Sutherland developed the first head-mounted display (HMD), called The Sword of Damocles [2]. The localization system had to be suspended from the ceiling due to the weight of the entire setup. Using an ultrasonic localization system, the software was able to track head movement and adjust the visuals displayed on the headset accordingly.

Later, in 1989, Jaron Lanier, often referred to as "the father of VR", coined the term Virtual Reality[3]. He worked at VPL Research and helped develop the VPL Eyephone, a PC-powered VR headset, along with a data glove that enabled gesture-based input.

In 1992, Thomas P. Caudell and David W. Mizell published a paper describing how a see-through headset could assist workers during assembly tasks [4]. In that paper, they introduced the term Augmented Reality to describe the concept. Today, both Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality fall under the broader term of technologies referred to as Extended Reality (XR), with a fluid transition between both technologies.

In 1995, Nintendo, a major player in the gaming console industry [5], attempted to release its first VR headset, the Nintendo Virtual Boy. Unfortunately, the technology was not advanced or attractive enough to be a commercial success. In the work of Boyer [6], the failure of the product is not described in binary terms of success or failure, but

rather as a fluid concept. Although the headset struggled due to its fixed viewing position, monochrome red LED display, limited software support, and relatively high price, it still managed to build a small but dedicated community of gamers and collectors. In retrospect, it also achieved a certain degree of success, but at that time it left a negative impression on consumers and the industry.

The first consumer-grade commercial headset was then the Oculus, which was crowd-funded with Kickstarter [7] in 2012. This led to the release of the headset in 2013. The success of the device led to the release of additional headsets in 2016–2017, such as the HTC Vive and the PlayStation VR system.

Today, VR headsets are growing in popularity every year [8]. The world market is expected to generate 10.48 billion US dollars in 2025. Comparing the years 2024 to 2030, a 27.26% increase in revenue globally is predicted. The anticipated increase in devices per person can explain this. This only includes commercially available headsets for end-users, such as an Oculus headset or a Valve Index. So, headsets for industrial applications, accessories such as controllers, and AR headsets are excluded from this prognosis.

2.1 Customisability of VR

Open-source headsets are not a new invention [9]. Several inventions have been made, such as the Relativity project [10]. This headset allows the user to print the headset and flash their microcontroller. With CAD files, the system can also be adapted to be used with other types of hardware. However, it is also limited in its use of tracking technologies. With only space for an imu and an Arduino controller, the space for testing different tracking systems is limited.

Another device that provided customizability was the OSVR [11]. This headset was created in 2015 in cooperation with Razer and Sencis. It provided open-source hardware and software that can be assembled with purchased components and expanded. However, this headset does not officially support OpenXR integration, which means that it requires separate software packages to enable SteamVR support and separate configurations when used in Unity and Unreal Engine. This makes it a less attractive competitor to other headsets with official OpenXR support. Furthermore, their case does not have adjustments like IPD and display-to-lens distance

The key feature of those open-source headsets is that they can be built at home. With the increase in popularity and availability of home 3D printers, such as the Bambu Lab printer [12], it becomes feasible for individuals to produce parts for their device at home [13]. Materials like polylactic acid (PLA), Polyethyleneterephthalat (PETG), and even wood filaments can be used to print individual elements for electronics. With this flexibility, headsets can be created based on the best material for the use case.

Additionally, with access to MakerSpaces and FabLabs *et al.* [14], people do not need to own a 3D printer to print their components. With CAD files provided by open-source headset projects, users can adapt and build their own versions, tailored to specific needs,

such as fitting a different display module or testing alternative optical systems.

Optical systems have a significant impact on the user's field of view (FOV) *et al.* [15]. In recent years, different technologies have emerged on the market, starting with simple aspheric lens systems, where multiple lenses were used to reduce chromatic aberration and improve image clarity for the user [16]. Later, Fresnel lenses were introduced into headset systems. One major reason for this shift was the reduction in lens thickness. Fresnel lenses are significantly thinner than traditional lenses, which allows for lighter and more compact headset designs. In addition to improved weight, these lenses also reduce manufacturing costs due to the lower material usage.

A more advanced optical system, as described by Bang [17], uses a lenslet array in combination with a Fresnel lens. This setup achieves a wide field of view of $108^\circ \times 108^\circ$ while only requiring a physical depth of 3.3mm between the display and the optics. Compared to traditional Fresnel lens systems, this is a significant improvement in compactness. However, the downside is the cost. Lenslet arrays are significantly more expensive than simple Fresnel lenses.

Pancake lens systems like the system of Narasimhan [18] are now well established in commercial headsets like the Oculus Quest 3, Oculus Quest Pro, Bigscreen Beyond, and many more. These systems use polarization-based reflection, where light rays bounce between two optical surfaces with the help of polarization filters. This allows for a more compact optical path than that of Fresnel lenses, but with the drawback of lower light efficiency because of losses introduced by the polarization elements.

One common requirement for all of these systems is, of course, lenses. Although most headsets rely on mass-produced lenses, there have been attempts to manufacture custom optics at home using 3D printing, as seen in the work of Alam *et al.* [19]. For this, resin printers are crucial, as they offer much higher precision than filament-based ones. After printing, the lens surface is sanded to reduce the visible layer steps from the printing process, but depending on the type of lens, for example, Fresnel lenses, this step cannot be done. In the work of Nair *et al.* [20], a Fresnel lens could be printed, although it was not perfect, the results were promising.

2.2 Standardization and Privacy

During the last 10 to 15 years, the VR headset market has undergone significant changes. Large companies like Meta and Valve, through their respective headsets (Meta's Quest and Valve's Steam), have developed their own unique ecosystems. This results in a less versatile environment for end-users but usually provides a more polished and controlled result. Open standards, such as OpenXR [21], released in 2019, aim to counteract this fragmentation. Several XR projects [22–25] and applications have since implemented the OpenXR standard to support more features. This not only helps to reach a broader user base, but also reduces development costs.

According to a Steam survey, one of the largest VR headset manufacturers for gaming

is Meta, with 29.10% using Meta Quest 2 and 22.66% using Meta Quest 3. Combined, this accounts for 51.76% of all headsets used on Steam, clearly placing Meta in the lead[26]. Meta adopted the OpenXR standard in 2021, discontinuing its API implementation [27]. This major change shows a shift in general API usage, from a time where each headset had to implement multiple standards, or even define its own, to a situation where developers can rely on OpenXR as a unified solution.

OpenXR also led to the creation of open-source OpenXR environments. An example is ILLIXR [28], a benchmark system built as an open testbed for scientific purposes. Its primary focus is on learning, experimenting and testing, rather than actual end-user applications. Another example is Monado [29], which provides a certified implementation of the OpenXR standard. Monado utilizes a modular system that allows different headsets and input devices to be connected, aiming to deliver a more practical and commercially viable experience rather than a purely scientific one. This framework is also used in ILLIXR to integrate the OpenXR standard.

These creations of open systems also have another benefit: the code can be viewed by security and privacy experts, and people have complete control over the data. Oculus VR (OVR) is the platform that Oculus uses to run its hardware. The code for this platform is not publicly available, like some of the OpenXR runtimes mentioned above. In Trimananda *et al.* [30], they test the network against privacy breaches and incorrect data handling of 140 individual apps. They noticed that most of the data usage is not disclosed in the privacy agreement if one exists.

2.3 Odometry and Tracking

In recent years, the development of accurate and robust pose estimation methods has been a major focus in VR development. Head tracking is crucial for an immersive user experience, as inaccuracies, delays, or stuttering can cause discomfort or even dizziness. In general, tracking systems can be grouped into three main categories: inertial-based, visual-based, and hybrid approaches, which combine both techniques.

Inertial-based systems typically rely on an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), which was also used in the first Oculus Rift headset [31] but only for rotational tracking. Since IMUs are relatively inexpensive, they are an attractive option for use in VR headsets. However, a major problem with IMU-only tracking is drift. Position and orientation are calculated by integrating acceleration and angular velocity values over time. Due to small sensor inaccuracies and numerical integration, these errors accumulate, causing the position to become increasingly incorrect over time. Some approaches attempt to improve accuracy by estimating bias and drift terms, as demonstrated in the works of Chen *et al.* [32] and Sabatini *et al.* [33]. Other approaches [34] focus on improving the internal sensor fusion algorithms to make better use of the available IMU data, which leads to more stable and precise results.

For visual tracking, the first commercial systems, like the Oculus Rift DK2[31], used

an Outside-In approach. External base stations were placed around the room, tracking infrared markers or LEDs mounted on the headset. This setup allowed the tracking system to determine the position and orientation of the headset based on camera input. Although this method offered good precision, it also had downsides, such as the requirement for a fixed setup and reduced portability, which can be seen in the work of Alanko [35].

For Inside-Out tracking, the cameras are mounted directly on the headset. This approach eliminates the need for external tracking stations, which reduces hardware requirements and costs, making the system compact and portable. Using simultaneous localization and mapping algorithms (SLAM), such as ORB-SLAM2 [36, 37], the system can calculate the head trajectory in real-time based on tracked 3D feature points. This enables real-time pose estimation without relying on an external infrastructure, which is ideal for mobile VR setups.

Hybrid tracking methods combine visual data with IMU data, using the strengths of both systems. Although the IMU provides high frequency updates, it suffers from drift over time. The SLAM system provides more stable and accurate pose estimates, but at a lower frequency. Combining both allows the system to correct the IMU drift using the visual SLAM data. These systems are commonly referred to as Visual-Inertial SLAM (VI-SLAM).

To improve performance and reduce computation time, Visual-Inertial Odometry (VIO) systems are often used instead of full SLAM. An example is the system proposed by Usenko *et al.* [38]. VIO systems cut out loop closure, the process of recognizing and correcting previously visited locations, to save processing power. This results in a less accurate map, but offers much better performance, which can be critical for real-time applications like VR.

Motivation and Requirements

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3.2 Requirements	12

The motivation behind this project arises from the inflexibility of modern headsets. For example, people with anisometropia suffer from a condition in which the diopter difference between the eyes is significant. In combination with a VR headset, which often does not allow for a comfortable fit when wearing glasses, this leads to a suboptimal experience.

The project therefore aims to provide a template and guidance for users who want to create a customized VR experience tailored to their personal needs. Based on this motivation, several key requirements were identified. Some of these were implemented in software, such as tracking the headset, while others were realized in hardware, for example, sealing against incoming light.

Figure 3.1: Varjo XR-4 Secure Edition

3.1 Motivation

Throughout the years, numerous adaptations of VR headsets have been developed. Creating various devices for different types of problem. Some devices, like the Oculus Quest series, are targeted at a broad consumer base as a budget-friendly, beginner-friendly headset. Some others, such as the Varjo XR-4 Secure Edition[39] seen in Figure 3.1, aim to provide high comfort, high usability, and high resolution for a specialized audience in fields such as medicine or architecture. These devices cost up to €26.990,00[40], which is not in the price range of a typical consumer. However, this is still a standard headset intended for individuals within a certain range of the norm.

A company that wants to sell customizable VR experiences is BigScreen VR[41], which takes a 3D Face Scan and uses it to create a customized fit around the user's head. This results in a perfect placement of the headset, which improves the overall experience.

3.1.1 Specialised Eye conditions

Certain conditions can prevent a person from perceiving stereoscopic vision. An example is monocular vision, where only one eye is functional, making stereo depth perception impossible. Another condition is anisometropia, characterized by a significant diopter difference between the two eyes. An illustration of the condition can be seen in Figure 3.2. Without specialized corrective lenses, users with such conditions cannot experience VR in the same way as the average user. However, with a customizable headset, it becomes possible to accommodate any lens or lens system. For example, a custom lens could be inserted to correct the difference in diopters, allowing the user to have a better VR experience in general.

Figure 3.2: On the right, we can see an eye that can keep an object in focus. This is achieved by setting the focal point on the retina of the eye. On the left eye, a strong deviation of the targeted focal point is illustrated. This strong difference in diopter is called anisometropia.

Another use case is accommodating users with non-normative head or eye geometries. For example, individuals with hypertelorism, an abnormally large distance between the eyes, may struggle to find a compatible VR headset, if any exists at all. If the IPD system cannot match the user's requirements, potential side effects include double vision, eye strain, or a complete inability to focus on the virtual image. With a modular system, the IPD can be individually adjusted, allowing customized alignment of the lenses and displays to meet the user's specific needs. This ensures a functional and comfortable VR experience even for users with unusual anatomical features.

3.1.2 Modular Design for Testing and Evaluation

The field of optics and displays is constantly evolving. Twenty years ago, some of the most popular display technologies were Liquid Crystal Displays (LCDs) and Plasma TVs. At the time, these were considered state-of-the-art and were widely used. Today, with the rise of OLED, QLED, Micro-LED, and other advanced technologies, these older panel types feel significantly outdated.

VR lens systems have also evolved, starting from as simple aspherical lenses and progressing to more modern designs such as pancake lenses. Pancake lenses are lighter than aspherical lenses and offer better visual quality compared to Fresnel lenses.

In addition, different tracking systems have their unique characteristics. For example, an optical RGB tracking system will not function correctly if there is insufficient lighting in the scene. When tracking with an inertial measurement unit, drift can occur over time, resulting in a position that does not accurately reflect the location of the real-world. Therefore, different scenarios require different technologies. Dark scenes, for example, can be tracked using an infrared camera in combination with a random pattern projector.

These changing requirements create the need for flexible testing solutions. To evaluate new display technologies, with or without specific optical paths, new hardware must be designed, tested, and validated. This results in redundant work hours, which can be optimized. With a testbed that already incorporates essential features, the development time can be reduced, allowing research into new technologies to progress more efficiently.

3.1.3 Shareable Components

As mentioned in the previous section, components can be altered and reused. When using a custom-fitted headset, both hardware and software should be able to adapt without requiring hours of adjustment. This would not only interrupt the user's experience, but also create additional obstacles for a more inclusive VR setup.

An easy replacement mechanism would enable the reuse of components, which also helps reduce e-waste, as individual parts can be sold or replaced separately. Furthermore, by enabling quick swapping of components, multiple users, such as those in a school setting, can share certain hardware when it is not needed simultaneously. In this way, some parts

can be specialized and custom-made for each person, while shared components help lower the acquisition cost per user.

This modular approach also enables for easier device repair. If some component fails, the replacement can be mounted without the need for specialized equipment. This can also be used to upgrade certain components without the need to discard the entire system.

3.1.4 Standardised Interface

A user browsing the internet relies on many standardized interfaces. These interfaces enable cross-application compatibility without requiring specialized implementations. Examples include the Universal Serial Bus (USB), the Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP), and the Compute Unified Device Architecture Runtime Application Programming Interface (CUDA Runtime API).

In the XR world, the OpenXR interface provides a similar function by enabling seamless communication between VR applications and hardware. Without such an interface, VR or AR applications developers would need to implement specialized code for each headset, resulting in significantly more work and higher development costs. It would also create a barrier for new headsets entering the market, as established devices would have a strong advantage due to developers already being familiar with their communication protocols.

3.2 Requirements

Based on the motivation discussed previously, a set of requirements was derived (see Table 3.1). These requirements aim to ensure that, if fully met, the project reaches a certain level of usability.

A major key point is the modular assembly of the system. It begins with a module that houses both the display and the lens (R1). This module should be designed to allow

Requirement	Description
R1	Replaceable lens system and display mounting
R2	Detachable compartment for optical tracking and miscellaneous electronics
R3	Displays are sealed against incoming light
R4	Separate adjustment system for inter-pupil distance and lens to display depth
R5	Usable in Windows to enable a broader user base
R6	Use a standardised interface for broader application compatibility
R7	Visual-Inertia Tracking for exemplary integration of a head tracking system in Windows

Table 3.1: Overview of the hardware and software requirements for the project. These requirements define the functional goals of the system.

for easy attachment and removal without requiring complete disassembly.

Another requirement, also falling into the category of modular systems, is the detachable compartment for the camera electronics and the camera mount (R2). As in the previous requirement, this compartment should be removable without major disassembly.

The core concept of the headset is customizability, allowing users to adjust it to their preferences. An adjustable IPD mechanism is necessary, as this parameter varies between users. Similarly, when using different lenses, the display-to-lens distance must be adjusted to account for varying focal lengths (R4).

Another key challenge is light leakage, which reduces immersion. To address this, the headset should be designed to minimize external light intrusion (R3).

However, the system does not end with hardware alone. Integration of software is also necessary for the VR system to work. To ensure compatibility with a wide range of applications, OpenXR support must be included (R6). This allows the headset to work even with applications that are not specifically designed for it. Furthermore, making the application accessible on Windows increases the potential user base (R5). Finally, a VR headset would not be functional without some form of positional tracking. Therefore, the system must include a way to adapt to various tracking methods (R7).

As a final summary, the goal of this project is to construct a modular VR headset with adjustable IPD and display-to-lens distance, as well as software integration that supports the OpenXR interface, is compatible with Windows and can adapt to different types of tracking systems.

Iterative Hardware Design

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Figure 4.1: Images of the individual headset prototypes starting from Iteration 1 to the final design.

This section documents the process of designing the headset. Using rapid prototyping as the foundational approach, the headset underwent many cycles of redesign and reevaluation, starting from a cardboard-only prototype without any electronics and evolving into a fully 3D-printed modular system. With each iteration, the additions and insights were documented and used to generate a requirement list for the next design cycle. Throughout each design cycle, new requirements were added to progressively move closer to the desired specification goals.

With this approach, new ideas can flow more easily into the headset’s system, while also enabling controlled direction and effective milestone tracking.

4.1 Cardboard - Iteration 1

The goal of the first prototype was to gain insight into the challenges and obstacles of designing a head-mounted display. Inspiration was drawn from the Oculus Rift [31] and Google Cardboard [42] to start the process. The concept involved designing a mounting bracket for the displays, allowing them to move back and forth (see Figure 4.2), and incorporating a Google Cardboard lens.

Ultimately, the prototype was not fully developed because the effort required exceeded the benefits. The conclusion was to utilize an existing solution, such as the Google Cardboard HMD, and to design mounting brackets to secure the displays behind the lenses. Two insights were concluded from this process. First, mounting the displays and lens system proved to be more complex than expected, especially since the goal was to have

Figure 4.2: In this left image, the first prototype of the display mount is shown. The idea was to mount the display using a slight press fit into the cardboard. While this was not the ideal solution, it helped generate future ideas and strategies for mounting. The right image shows the mounting of the lens holder, indicated by the white arrow. The cardboard strap can be pushed or pulled to adjust the distance between the display and the eyes.

a replaceable lens system. Second, designing an adjustable inter-eye distance mechanism requires careful use of space to avoid obstructing the user's view.

Learning 1

Creating a cardboard prototype is a feasible step for identifying potential obstacles early in development, which can lead to fewer iteration cycles, even if the cardboard solution is not ultimately successful.

4.2 Google Cardboard - Iteration 2

As a second iteration, Google Cardboard was used as a base, with the idea of replacing the smartphone holder with two separate displays. This led to the creation of the first mounting brackets for the displays and breakout boards, as shown in Figure 4.3. This

(a) display holder

(b) mounting bracket for breakoutboard

(c) cardboard cover open

(d) cardboard cover closed

Figure 4.3: (a) To secure the displays in place, separate mounting brackets were glued onto the cardboard. The mounting technique used a simple slot-in mechanism, where the display was inserted from the top and held in place by the connection cable. (b) On the back, another bracket was glued to hold the breakout board for each display. (c) Both mounts were attached to the backside flap of the Google Cardboard, which can be opened. (d) Closed side of the headset .

iteration also introduced 3D printing into the project, which, due to its accessibility and speed, enabled faster prototyping and improved the design process.

Since the displays lacked mounting holes, they were slotted into the holders from the top and secured at the bottom by the connection cables. The breakout board brackets were designed similarly, with the boards held in place by their connection cables. For each side of the headset, a display holder and a breakout board holder were required, both of which were glued to the surface of the cardboard headset. The prototype was tested with two pre-rendered images, which produced a stereoscopic effect when looking through the lenses.

Mounting of the display and breakout board with the current holder proved to be a feasible solution and could be implemented in future iterations. However, the tolerance of the holder was too loose, resulting in small positional deviations of up to 2 millimeters, which is critical for this immersive application. In addition, the displays tended to pop out of their sockets due to the loose fit. The driver board was still left hanging freely because the Google Cardboard did not have sufficient space for it. Furthermore, the headset cardboard hinge was slightly damaged from repeated opening and closing of the flap, leading to the conclusion that cardboard would not be suitable as a base material for future prototypes.

Learning 2

The displays should not move and be well seated or screwed, as this breaks user immersion and causes discomfort when wearing.

4.3 Introduction of 3D Printing - Iteration 3

To increase the stability and durability of the headset, plastic was used in this iteration, making it the first 3D-printed headset in the design process. For development, PLA was chosen as the material, as it is one of the most widely used, reliable, and fastest materials for 3D printing [43]. Most of the design work was done in a CAD program called Fusion 360 [44], where the entire design process was digitalized. The model files were then transferred to a slicer, which divides the model into individual layers and calculates the path of the printhead.

This prototype, visible in Figure 4.4, also introduced Fresnel lenses, with the challenge of determining their focal length. A system was designed that allows for manual adjustment of the distance between the lens and the display. A lens bracket was created to hold the Fresnel lens and a floor plate was used to secure the brackets. The displays were mounted on a sliding plate that allowed movement back and forth. By adjusting the distance between the display and the lens, the focal length was roughly measured by finding the point where the display appeared sharp to the eye.

Figure 4.4: (a) The display holders are designed to hold the Fresnel lenses in place without restriction. (b) To determine the focal length of the lenses, the mounting point for the displays can be adjusted, moving back and forth.

With the approximate focal distance, the next iteration can implement a more reliable method to adjust it. The sliding display system was unfeasible, as the clamps that secure the displays to the floorboard were too fragile. To stabilize the lenses, a top piece would be required to support the upper holding bracket. This improvement would also improve the overall stability of the design, allowing for a mounting plate for the driver boards. A dedicated holder would be useful for future development.

Learning 3

3D printing is a viable solution to produce parts for a headset. This leads to fast development and more flexible prototyping with a sturdy build quality.

4.4 Designing a Case - Iteration 4

With the introduction of iteration 4, the lenses were now fully encased, which locked them in place while also allowing swapping of lenses. Compared to the previous iterations, the displays are locked in place, and the lenses are now free to move and can be individually spaced. In addition, to improve stability and support the lens holder, a top cover was designed.

A big issue with all designs was that the driver board was not held in place. With the introduction of a compartment at the bottom, the driver board can be inserted into it. In Figure 4.5, an CAD design of the headset is illustrated. Although this approach worked well for earlier prototypes, it was insufficient for this iteration. As the first version

Figure 4.5: (a) The lenses are now fully encased and have a fixed seat. This was done by adding a top cover to support the upper bracket of the lens holder. (b) A holder for the driver board was introduced on the bottom side of the HMD. This allowed the headset to mount all the needed electronics.

was capable of housing all electrical components, this iteration could be picked up, which placed additional stress on certain joints. As a result, the use of glue is not a future-proof solution and will need to be replaced with a more durable assembly method. Additionally, the placement of the driver compartment on the bottom of the device was impractical and should be relocated to a more functional position in future iterations.

Learning 4

Even on prototypes, a sturdy build is a must otherwise, the user needs to handle it very carefully, and problems that can arise from improper handling are not noticed.

4.5 Stability Improvement - Iteration 5

In the previous iteration, stability was a major issue. This was resolved by replacing most of the glued joints with screws, which improved the strength of the joints. A total of 12 screws were used to secure nine individual parts. While the majority of glue joints were replaced, the display mounting bracket and breakout board mounting bracket were still glued. In order to secure the screws, nuts and press inserts were used.

The driverboard holder was relocated to the back of the HMD. Because this location blocked the breakout board bracket, the driver board compartment was redesigned to be detachable and secured with two screws. With this change, the device's footprint was significantly reduced. Additionally, the tolerances of the individual parts were reworked

Figure 4.6: In (a), we can see that the top of the HMD now has screws on top where the distance between the display and lens can be adjusted. (b) The backside has also changed with a detachable slot where the driver board can be inserted .

and improved. One significant issue is light leakage into the headset, which reduces the overall immersive experience. In addition, there are several problems with the driver board compartment. First, simply slotting the board into the compartment is not a feasible solution, as it risks damaging the board. It needs to be securely fixed in place. Second, the compartment lid is not sufficiently secured with just one bolt. Finally, the ports on the driver board are not easily accessible, making it difficult to connect the cables. The result of this iteration is visible in Figure 4.6

Learning 5

A sturdy and fixed build is essential for a headset to reduce wear and tear on the components and to provide a better experience for the user. Additionally, the display must be shielded from incoming light, as any light leakage breaks the illusion.

4.6 Final Design

In the final design (see Figure 4.7), all the requirements of R1 to R5 are met. The entire headset is designed to be easily disassembled and reassembled, allowing multiple parts to be replaced and adapted. This is necessary to fulfill requirements R1 and R2. Furthermore, a camera mount and a compartment for other electronics were added to the back of the device to fulfill requirement 5. The displays and lenses themselves have a module that is sealed against incoming light and therefore fulfills R3. For the IPD configuration, each

Figure 4.7: (a) The front of the device houses the two separate eye modules. The top provides the mechanism for the adjustable IPD system. (b) On the back side, the electronics compartment and the camera are mounted .

eye has its own lens module, which can be moved individually.

Furthermore, the module also features a gear system that allows one to adjust the distance between the image display. Most of the parts can be made with 3D printing. Some exceptions include the threaded rods for the lens module and the threaded inserts with screws for assembling the entire system.

4.6.1 Lense Module

The lens module can be divided into two main components: the inner module and the outer housing. The inner module houses the lens and display and contains the mechanism that adjusts the distance between them. The outer housing seals the entire assembly against light, incorporates the adjustment wheel used to set the lens-to-display spacing, provides mounting points for the MIPI-to-HDMI board on the rear, and also has a sliding system for the case. Some gears link the outer adjustment wheel to the two internal threaded rods, translating rotary motion into precise linear travel. The inner housing itself is made up of four parts.

4.6.1.1 Inner Component

The inner module houses the lens and display, and contains the mechanism that adjusts the distance between them. This setup involves placing the breakout board and display on a plate that secures both components near each other (see Figures 4.8 (a) and (b)). A slight change compared to the previous iteration is that the breakout board is now fixed in place with screws instead of a bracket that allows the board to slide in.

To guide the display plate and simplify installation, two dovetail slides were added: the dovetail bases are mounted to the top and bottom covers (see Figure 4.8 (c)), while the

Figure 4.8: (a) To secure the display, we retained the plate-mounting bracket from the previous iteration. (b) The breakout board is now fastened with screws rather than a separate mounting bracket. (c) The lens-holder system remains largely unchanged, but the top and bottom covers are now fused with the lens holder, and a dovetail slide was also added for the display plate. (d) Once assembled with the backplate, the complete inner assembly appears as shown in the image.

matching saddles are on the plate itself. In the final design, each lens-mounting bracket is combined with its corresponding cover in a single unit, replacing the two separate parts used previously and reducing the overall part count for an easier assembly process. A backplate secured by four screws seals the module from the back. The dovetail bases include holes for inserting threaded inserts. With them in place, the backplate can be fixed with 4 screws to the assembly.

To transfer the rotational motion of the adjustment wheel into linear movement, the threaded rods are combined with gears to form a simple lead-screw mechanism. The display plate was designed to house two threaded inserts, into which the rods are screwed, enabling the movement of the plate. To reduce wobble, the free ends of the rods are seated in the lens holder, fixing them in place while still allowing rotation. Furthermore, the rods were placed on the diagonal end to keep the plate still. The backplate has two holes for the rods to pass through, allowing the gear to remain accessible from the outside. Three separate gears were added to allow the two gears for the rods to be turned in sync, ensuring equal travel on both sides, which is crucial for the mechanism. A small feature that should not be overlooked is the small insertion on top, which allows the flat cable to exit from the inside.

4.6.1.2 Outer Component

The outer component is a shell-like structure in which the inner component can slide in (see Figure 4.9). This shell is optimized in a way that makes it easy to 3D print. It provides a partitioning between the gears for the adjustment of the display and the adjustment wheel, which the user can access. This separation is also intended to stop the gears from falling off the backplate.

Before inserting the inner component, the flat cable should be routed through the

Figure 4.9: (a) The module consists of two main parts: the outer component seen on the left side and the inner component on the right. The inner component can still be pushed slightly inward to complete the assembly. In Image (b), the parts are fully combined, with the lid placed on top to protect the chamber from incoming light. (c) The final component is the driver board on the back. The board is mounted backwards, as the cable exits in that direction.

large hole on top to simplify the installation process. This hole is intentionally larger to allow the cable to maintain a wider bending radius when installed. After the inner component has been installed, a plate is screwed on to seal the open side and prevent any light from entering. The locations where the screws are inserted serve another purpose as well. Similar to the display plate, the lens module features a dovetail slide that fits into the case, located at the top and bottom.

To enable IPD adjustment, the outer case includes a small knob on the top with a hole designed to accommodate a pressed-in threaded insert. This forms the connection point for the mechanism that moves the entire module. On the back of the case are three mounting points, which can be used to secure the driver board to the case.

4.6.2 Case

The case itself consists of only three individual parts: two side covers and one housing. The side covers are fixed to the sides of the housing with four screws. This gives the overall system a cleaner look, prevents modules from falling out if the IPD system fails, and can be adapted to add mounting points for headtraps. On top of the case, there are several raised sections. These sections are part of the IPD system that facilitates the movement of modules. The lower bumps support the rails and apply slight upward pressure to them. There are also two types of larger raised features. The sloped rectangular bumps guide the rails to prevent unwanted movement. The circular bump holds the adjustment wheel for the IPD system.

On the bottom of the housing, there are slots that provide access to the adjustment wheel for the display-to-lens distance. At the beginning of these slots, there are indenta-

(a) top of the device

(b) bottom of the device

Figure 4.10: (a) On the top side of the case, the complete IPD adjustment system is visible, including the rack-and-pinion mechanism. The gear rack is directly connected to the lens module, allowing it to slide for adjustment. To ensure it follows the intended linear path, raised guide features are integrated into the case. Without these, the rack would deviate from its path during movement. (b) On the bottom side, the HDMI and power ports are accessible through dedicated openings. Additionally, two slots are cut out to provide access to the adjustment wheel. To ensure the device stands securely on flat surfaces, small feet have been added to the bottom of the case.

tions that serve two purposes: first, to allow the adjustment wheel to pass through and second, to improve the overall stability of the system. Without these indentations, the bottom would be connected only at a single point in the middle, which could easily lead to structural failure. Another use, which was not originally intended, is that they also serve as feet on which the entire device can stand. That is also why a single line was added with matching height.

The HDMI and power ports of the driver boards can also be seen and connected below. On the back side, there are four holes for mounting a compartment. This allows for a more flexible solution when it comes to swapping out the tracking electronics.

4.6.3 Camera Mount and Electronics Compartment

As mentioned in the previous subsection, the back of the case features four rectangular cutouts intended to secure an additional compartment (see Figure 4.7b). This connection utilizes a snap-fit mechanism, where the hooks in the compartment align with the cutouts and lock into place upon insertion. On the bottom side of the compartment, a cutout allows cables to be routed when needed. For example, when used as a standalone device, it could house a micro PC. In this project, the compartment is used to house a USB hub. In addition, the back of the compartment includes two holes for mounting a camera using screws. If the compartment needs to be removed or replaced, the snap-fit mechanism can be released by pressing simultaneously on the top and bottom.

4.6.4 IPD Adjustment

For IPD adjustment, a separate mechanism was designed on top of the case, which connects to the lens module. As mentioned in Section 4.6.1.2, the outer shell of the lens module has a small knob on the top side that houses a threaded insert. This knob is the connection point for the mechanism. To reach it from the outside, a capsule formed hole was cut into the top of the hull. This allows a connection piece to attach to the knob and be secured with a screw. In addition, the connection piece has a linear rack attached to it, which can be moved using a rack and pinion mechanism. The gear on top acts as the dial to set the IPD.

To lock the current adjusted IPD, a screw on the top can be fastened, which presses down on the attachment plate that holds the adjustment screw in place. The system can be seen in Figure 4.10

4.7 Discussion of Hardware

In this section, hardware creation is discussed. Starting from the international process of creating the headset. Explaining how certain iterations impacted the final iteration and how the individual requirements were met in the end. Furthermore, the headset itself is compared to other consumer-grade headsets with respect to certain features.

4.7.1 Iterations

In the previous sections, six iterations of the device have been presented. The process began with a simple cardboard model that did not have functionality. This non-functional prototype was created to gain a better understanding of the most significant challenges and obstacles. An issue that was initially underestimated was the adjustability of the distance between the display and the lens. Before building the prototype, this issue seemed minor, but during the process of assembling the cardboard box, it became clear that handling all requirements (see Table 3.1) would be more complex than expected. This early insight allowed the design process to be adjusted early on.

The second iteration introduced a basic working prototype, which was still primarily made of cardboard. With the help of 3D printing, specialized components can be added to hold electronic parts, such as displays. This version enabled the first successful test of the stereoscopic effect. However, the prototype was still fragile. It could not support any tracking components and was not stable enough to be picked up or handled reliably.

The third iteration eliminated the use of cardboard and employed only 3D-printed parts that were glued together. One of the main improvements in this version was the introduction of an adjustable mechanism for the display-to-lens distance. This was used to experimentally determine the correct focal length for the Fresnel lenses, which were also introduced in this version. However, while the lens adjustment was effective, the overall build remained very unstable. The glued parts could not hold their position under stress,

and the prototype was not durable enough for regular handling. With the measurements and learnings from the last iteration, the fourth version was created. It featured a more solid adjustable system for the display-to-lens distance, which was now within the usable range of the lenses. A compartment was also added for all electronics, allowing the entire device to be picked up and handled as a single unit. One major issue that remained was the use of glue. In real-world usage, especially with rough handling, the glued joints could not withstand stress and started to fail. This made the structure unreliable and highlighted the need for a better solution.

In iteration 5, the form factor of the headset was improved. By introducing a detachable system on the back of the headset, the driver board compartment could be moved there. Furthermore, most of the components were new and were attached with screws, which significantly improved the stability of the system. The only components glued were the display and the breakout board holder.

In Table 4.1, the individual learnings from each iteration are listed. These learnings were directly considered in the final design of the headset. The design consists of a modular system composed of four main parts: two eye modules, one compartment for additional hardware, and a central case that holds everything together.

Each eye module includes mounting points for electrical components. In addition to housing the electronics, the modules also integrate the lenses. A key feature of these parts is the dial wheel mechanism, which allows the user to adjust the distance between the display and the lens. With this, requirements 1 and 3 are fulfilled, and the depth adjustment aspect of requirement 4 is satisfied.

The electronics compartment is designed with a simple snap-on system, allowing the

Learning 1	Creating a cardboard prototype is a feasible step for identifying potential obstacles early in development, which can lead to fewer iteration cycles, even if the cardboard solution is not ultimately successful.
Learning 2	The displays should not move and be well seated or screwed, as this breaks user immersion and causes discomfort when wearing.
Learning 3	3D printing is a viable solution to produce parts for a headset. This leads to fast development and more flexible prototyping with a sturdy build quality.
Learning 4	Even on prototypes, a sturdy build is a must otherwise, the user needs to handle it very carefully, and problems that can arise from improper handling are not noticed.
Learning 5	A sturdy and fixed build is essential for a headset to reduce wear and tear on the components and to provide a better experience for the user. Additionally, the display must be shielded from incoming light, as any light leakage breaks the illusion.

Table 4.1: The learnings over each iteration, which were incorporated into the last design.

	Meta Quest 3	Valve Index	PS VR2	Our Solution
Release Year	2023	2019	2023	2025
Type	Standalone	PC	Console	PC
Resolution per Eye	2064 × 2208	1440 × 1600	2000 × 2040	<u>1600x1600</u>
Max. Refresh Rate	120 Hz	144 Hz	120 Hz	<u>90 Hz</u>
FOV	≈ 110°	108°	≈ 110°	<u>≤ 90</u>
Tracking	Inside-out	Outside-in	Inside-out	<u>Inside-out</u>
IPD Adjustment	53–75 mm	58–70 mm	58-73 mm	<u>64-83 mm</u>
Weight	515 g	809 g	560 g	<u>568g</u>
Fully Customisable	No	No	No	Yes

Table 4.2: A comparison of existing headsets and our solution. The one thing to keep in mind is that the panels and lenses are swappable, this means some metrics are dependent on the configuration. The best values are highlighted in bold, while values that can be changed through swapping of components are underlined.

module to be attached to the back of the case without tools. It can be customized according to the components used and satisfies requirement 2.

The central case forms the core of the system. It contains the IPD adjustment system, which is another aspect of requirement 4. In addition, it includes dovetail rails to mount the eye modules and snap-on slots for the rear electronics compartment, making it the part that connects and holds the entire headset together.

4.7.2 Comparison of the Final Design

In Table 4.2, the final hardware is compared to some existing commercial headsets. For this comparison, the Valve Index from 2019, the Meta Quest 3 and the PS VR2 were selected. These headsets span a wider range of release dates and specifications, which allows a better comparison of the prototype within the hardware that is on the market. The table lists individual features where the best values are highlighted in bold. Features that can be adjusted or customized are underlined to indicate their flexibility.

Because technology is growing rapidly, the release years were mentioned to have a better reference point for comparison. Our solution is PC-based, meaning that a Computer needs to be connected to render the image, which is then displayed on the headset. For other headsets, the methods are console-based, where the headset is connected to a gaming console like the PlayStation, and Standalone, where the headset itself can render the image and does not need a separate device for this.

Compared to other headsets, the resolution per eye is not comparable to that of Meta Quest 3. Our solution is significantly lower and more comparable to the Valve Index. The

reason for this is the off-the-shelf screens, which are not capable of providing a higher resolution. For the refresh rate, the Valve Index is the leader with 144 Hz, which is higher than most headsets on the market. Comparing this refresh rate with the Meta Quest 3 and the PS VR2, which both have a maximum refresh of 120Hz. The reason for this may be that the Valve Index has a significantly lower resolution than Meta Quest 3 and PS VR2. Our solution has a refresh rate of 90 Hz, where the panels are the limitation.

The FOV cannot be measured correctly but is estimated to be less than 90°, which is not really a competitive solution. This value is influenced by the combination of the lens and the display, for example, a lens that has a smaller focal length influences the distance between the lens and the display, and the closer the display, the higher the FOV. Also, when the display is not wide enough, the FOV shrinks because the user can see areas where the display is not prominent.

For tracking, an Inside-Out solution was easier to implement and used less setup than Outside-In tracking. Although inside-out tracking is more mobile, Outside-In tracking is more robust and accurate. In addition, IPD adjustment is an important feature of a headset, as incorrect IPD can cause discomfort to the user. While the Meta Quest 3 has the largest range, our solution can reach a higher maximum distance, but on the other hand, the minimum is quite high compared to other headsets. This can be explained by the width of the lens modules, which are 3D printed.

The lightest headset in this comparison is the Meta Quest 3, with a weight of 515g. This is comparable to our solution, which has about 52g more. When compared to older models like the Valve Index, the whole system is much lighter, which is, of course, beneficial to the user.

Although our headset is not outstanding in a specific feature, one thing that stands out among all other features is the aspect of customization. By being able to switch out a display for one with much higher resolution and better frame rate, the headset could compare or even outperform an Oculus Rift 3. With the option to swap out the lens, the system can also increase its field of view.

By being able to swap out different electronics, the headset can be equipped with an Inside-Out tracking system or an Outside-In system, depending on the circumstances. This also means that the headset can be adjusted to accommodate a wider range of IPD adjustment.

Software implementation

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5.1 Proof of Concept

Figure 5.1: Software structure of the initial prototype. This describes the path of odometry data from its generation at the RGBD device to its processing and rendering at the stereo camera system. The different colors describe different Software component types. At the bottom of the image, the meaning of the individual colors are displayed.

The goal of the prototype was to create a knowledge base. It was built to achieve a first working prototype as fast as possible, so a majority of the code and technologies were

Figure 5.2: Cameras used for evaluation and comparison.

not well-designed up front. In Figure 5.1, the whole pipeline is displayed starting from the top right corner, where the RGBD camera is capturing RGB and depth images. In the driver script, the system received the individual images, which are used to calculate a relative position change compared to the previous image data. The change in position is transformed into a transformation matrix, serialized, and sent over a publish/subscribe connection to a Unity application, where it gets received by a subscriber.

Because Unity only allows interactions with its application through the main thread, a main thread dispatcher is introduced to forward the transformation data to the stereo camera implementation. The position of the individual cameras is transformed by the transformation matrix. This can result in a change in the rotation and position of the stereo camera system. Unity renders the individual frames in full-screen mode on the individual displays, allowing the user to view the rendering through the headset. In this section, each component of this prototype is described in more detail.

5.1.1 RGBD Camera Driver

To obtain RGBD data, a suitable camera must be selected. Initially, a variety of RGBD cameras were tested in terms of their specifications. This includes the Orbbec Astra Embedded S, Structure Core ST02D-C, Orbbec Astra and the Intel Realsense D435i (see Figure 5.2). Some specifications can be seen in Table 5.1.

Starting with the Astra and Astra Embedded S, there is no substantial difference

Camera Model	Depth Camera	RGB Camera	FOV (H×V)	Weight
Orbbec Astra	640×480 @ 30 fps	640×480 @ 30 fps	58.4° × 45.5°	310 g
Orbbec Astra Embedded S	1280×800 @ 30 fps; 640×400 @ 60 fps	1920×1080 @ 30 fps	67.9° × 45.3°	27 g
Structure Core ST02D-C	1280×960 @ 54 fps	640×480 @ 100 fps	49° × 46°	52.5 g
Intel RealSense D435i	1280×720 @ 30 fps (up to 90 fps)	1920×1080 @ 30 fps	87° × 58°	72 g

Table 5.1: Specifications of investigated cameras

between them in terms of resolution and frame rate for the RGB sensor. However, the depth camera of the Astra Embedded S has a significantly higher resolution than that of the Astra. A major drawback of the Astra is its weight of 310g and dimensions of 165mm x 48mm x 40mm (width x height x depth), making it too large and heavy for a headset. In comparison, the Astra Embedded S, weighing just 27g with dimensions of 69mm x 22.9mm x 15mm, clearly outperforms the Astra in terms of size and weight.

Deciding whether the Structure Core ST02D-C is a better choice than the Intel RealSense D435i depends on comparing their specifications. The RealSense depth camera has a framerate of up to 90 fps, a resolution of up to 1280x720, and a field of view of 87°,×,58°. The ST02D-C has a framerate of up to 60 fps, a resolution of up to 1280x960, and a field of view of 49°,×,46°. The RGB camera of the Structure Core ST02D-C can record at a resolution of 640x480 with 100 fps, while the D435i records at 1920x1080 with 30 fps.

One key factor that was not mentioned is the compatibility and ease of use. The Intel Realsense D435i is widely supported throughout the industry and used by many technical companies. For this use case, the D435i was chosen over the Structure Core ST02D-C because of the ease of integration and native support with multiple libraries.

The last decision was to choose between the Astra embedded S and the Intel Realsense D435i. The choice fell on the Intel camera not only because of its better software support but also because of its superior specifications. Although the Astra camera weighs 27g and the Intel camera 72g, the improved depth accuracy, wider field of view, and more robust SDK of the Intel RealSense D435i outweigh the benefit of a lighter device. With the camera fixed, the driver can now be written. To create a fast-working prototype, Python

```
1 def getImage(pipeline, align):
2     frames = pipeline.wait_for_frames()
3     aligned_frames = align.process(frames)
4     depth_frame = aligned_frames.get_depth_frame()
5     color_frame = aligned_frames.get_color_frame()
6     if not depth_frame or not color_frame:
7         return [], []
8
9     depth_image = np.asanyarray(depth_frame.get_data())
10    color_image = np.asanyarray(color_frame.get_data())
11    return depth_image, color_image
```

Listing 1: The following code retrieves an image from the camera and returns it as a NumPy array. First, the images are obtained from the pipeline. To compensate for the spatial discrepancy between streams, an alignment process is applied in line 3. Afterward, each image is checked to ensure it is not None. If either image is missing, a set of empty lists is returned, signaling the caller to skip the frame. If everything functions correctly, the images are converted into NumPy arrays and returned.

was used with the PyRealsense2 library. By connecting the RGBD device with a USB cable, the program can read the live image data and also the intrinsic camera parameters.

Before the driver could retrieve the device images, a software pipeline had to be instantiated from the library. First, the USB connection to the device was established. Then, parameters such as the frame rate, the number of streams (in our case, two: one for RGB and one for depth images) and the depth scale had to be set. Afterward, the pipeline can be opened and the images can be retrieved.

In the code snippet 1, the retrieval of depth and RGB images is demonstrated. First, both images are obtained from the device in line 1. Afterward, they are aligned, as they originate from different viewports and are slightly shifted. The alignment process corrects for this discrepancy. If one of the streams is empty, the entire frame is skipped, as indicated by the return statement on line 7. Finally, both images are converted into NumPy arrays and returned for further processing.

5.1.2 Pose Tracking

The Open3D library was used for pose tracking. This enables us to estimate the movement and rotation between frames and therefore, allows us to transmit this data further on to Unity. Open3D has two algorithms implemented for use in odometry. In this case, the default value is sufficient because first of all this is a prototype which does not need to be efficient and second, the developers of Open3D already benchmarked the algorithms and concluded that the algorithm of Park *et al.* [45] takes as long as Steinbrucker *et al.* [46] but has more accurate results [47].

In Listing2, the Open3D function call is shown. However, before we can call this function, an RGBDImage object must be instantiated from the current data pair. With this object, we can call the function with the previous and current RGBD images. This results in an Open3D results object, which can be transformed into a numpy matrix. It represents the transformation matrix from the source frame to the target frame. By scaling the translation part of the matrix by 10, the movement in the x,y, and z directions is amplified for better visualization purposes. This matrix gets serialized to JSON notation and can now be transferred to Unity.

```

1 result = o3d.t.pipelines.odometry.rgbd_odometry_multi_scale
2         (source_rgbd_image, target_rgbd_image, o3d_intrinsics)

```

Listing 2: Function call for RGBD odometry. The parameters from left to right are the RGBDImage object holding the previous frame, the RGBDImage object holding the current frame, and the camera intrinsics.

5.1.3 Interaction between Unity and Driver

To establish data transfer between Unity and the driver, a simple networking approach was used. Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) was chosen to send the data to Unity. The goal was to create a replaceable pose estimation system that could function independently of a specific driver. Thanks to MQTT's publish-subscribe model, this is possible. Unity does not need to know the data source. It simply subscribes to a predetermined topic, allowing any connected client to publish data to the broker.

5.1.3.1 Driver integration

In Python, a library called `paho.mqtt` handles the connection. After the client has been initialized, it connects itself to `localhost`, where the broker is hosted. The broker used is Eclipse Mosquitto. A simple Docker Compose file was created to start the broker. A small config file has been written to allow the broker to start. After establishing the connection between the driver and the broker, the data of the matrix can now be sent on to a predetermined topic. In this, the topic was called "odometry".

5.1.3.2 MQTTnet in Unity

In the C# environment, the NuGet package manager provides an MQTT library called MQTTnet. However, Unity does not natively support NuGet packages. Fortunately, a Unity plugin called NuGetForUnity [48] enables the installation of NuGet packages, including MQTTnet [49]. By instantiating an MQTT client and specifying connection parameters, such as IP address, port, and client name, the program can connect to the broker. When subscribing to a topic, a callback function must be provided that can handle the data.

During initial testing, a simple transformation was applied to a cube, but the function call did not modify the cube. The reason for this issue was that the function was not executed from the Unity main thread. To resolve this problem, a separate Unity object was created with a Main Thread Dispatcher script attached. This script allowed tasks to be appended to a queue, and each time Unity's Update function was called, a task was dequeued and executed within the main thread. This allowed the function to be scheduled to the Unity main thread. From there, the data could now interact with objects in the Unity scene.

5.1.4 Unity integration

The first challenge was to configure two cameras to display on separate screens using Unity. The scripting API allows calls to the variable `Camera.targetDisplay`, which defines the target display to which the camera is rendering.

To establish a common rotation point, which serves as the camera's point of origin, both cameras are placed within the same parent. The script for setting the camera target

Figure 5.3: (a) The two cameras are displayed in the Unity viewport. This visualization makes the program debugging easier because the headset’s movement is visible. (b) The image shows the script parameters. There is one parameter for each camera to let the script know which cameras are being used. One parameter is for the inter-eye distance, which refers to the relative distance between the two cameras. The last two checkboxes function as buttons that can be clicked to reset the position and rotation.

displays is also put onto the parents. After exposing the two camera variables from the script to the inspector, both cameras can be placed into separate fields, one for the left eye and one for the right eye.

In addition, the position of the individual cameras needs to be controlled. The relative position of these two cameras should be within the range of the mean IPD, which is approximately 5.9 to 6.6 cm [50]. Both cameras are placed $\pm 1/2$ of the IPD on the x-axis of the parent object, leaving them at the IPD relative to each other. This distance should also correspond to the physical IPD.

With the whole system now, a function can be set where the JSON matrix can get parsed to a Matrix4x4 object. By extracting the translational part and the vector where your camera is facing, the position of the headset can be updated. We do not care about scale and shear because the odometry result does not produce scale or shear. To visualize content on the displays, the Unity test scene was imported. The resulting unity UI is shown in Figure 5.3, and renderings of the results are presented in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: The final rendered view of the left and the right.

5.2 Integration of OpenXR driver

Figure 5.5: The diagram shows a more advanced solution consisting of multiple additions. With the introduction of an IMU, which is included in the camera, an algorithm combining the Infrared camera and the inertia and gyroscope values is needed. This is done through a Visual-Inertial SLAM system. The relative position changes get processed and sent to the application through the OpenXR standard. The OpenXR loader passes the data forward to the individual applications. An OpenXR Application can be any application that uses the OpenXR specification to communicate with the headset. From there, the applications rendered images get rendered onto a render target, which is provided by the OpenXR loader through the OpenXR runtime, where the driver is located. These render targets can then be displayed.

In this section, the software is extended by the Khronos OpenXR standard. Using the standardization leads to multiple benefits, which are mentioned in section 3. To avoid unnecessary implementation, the open-source project Monado was forked and adapted to incorporate another device driver. This led to a series of additions to incorporate the device into the system. Further additions for Windows support have been implemented to enable compilation and dynamic loading of shared libraries, which are used to load VI-Slam. In this system, the library Basalt, based on the work of Usenko *et al.* [38], is loaded into the system, which also requires adaptations for Windows to enable the DLL compilation process to work. In the end, the software produces a window that displays separate views for each eye. This window is mapped onto the displays for the finished

```
1     sed -r -e 's/sample_hmd/custom_vr/g' \  
2     -e 's/\bsh\b/cvr/g' \  
3     -e 's/sample_auto_prober/custom_vr_auto_prober/g' \  
4     -e 's/\bsap\b/cvrap/g' \  
5     -e 's/\bSH_/CVR_/g' \  
6     -e 's/sample/custom_vr/g' \  
7     -e 's/SAMPLE/CUSTOM_VR/g' \  
8     -i *.c *.h
```

Listing 3: To speed up the process of renaming all variables in the sample files for the driver, a `sed` command was used to rename most of the occurrences, which was suggested in the documentation of `Monado`.

product. In Figure 5.5, the whole system is illustrated.

5.2.1 Creating a device driver

To register a new device in `Monado`, a separate library object must be created that contains the specific implementations of the device. The developers of `Monado` already provide a sample driver, which lies in the `src/xrt/drivers/sample` directory, consisting of three files:

- `sample_hmd.c` - implements the creation of a new device object
- `sample_interface.h` - defines the C interface
- `sample_prober.c` - implements the detection of the hardware

The first step was to copy all sample files into a directory called `src/xrt/drivers/custom_vr`, where all the driver files will be located. A `sed` command (see Listing 3) helped to replace the naming in the original three files. However, to compile those files, the `CMake` file located in the `custom_vr` folder's directory, which builds all the device libraries, was also expanded to build a library. This library is called `drv_custom_vr` and compiles with the files `custom_vr_device.c`, `custom_vr_prober.c`, `custom_vr_interface.h`. So, the prober file contains a few functions, but the most prominent one is the function `custom_vr_create_auto_prober`. This function creates an autoprobe that should automatically find a fitting device when an `OpenXR` application is started. But in order to even create a device, a function called `custom_vr_create` is defined in the `custom_vr_device.c` file, which implements the functionality of creating a new device instance of the `CustomVR` driver. This function basically sets all the necessary callbacks and variables for the device, for example, the `FOV`, framerate of the display, and size of the display in pixels. This also includes the parameters for the distortion model, which can be manually tuned using a checkerboard pattern on the display and by adjusting the lines to be straight through the `VR` glasses.

```
1  if(XRT_BUILD_DRIVER_CUSTOM_VR)
2      add_library(
3          drv_custom_vr STATIC
4          custom_vr/custom_vr_device.c
5          custom_vr/custom_vr_prober.c
6          custom_vr/custom_vr_interface.h
7      )
8      target_link_libraries(drv_custom_vr PRIVATE
9          xrt-interfaces )
10     list(APPEND ENABLED_DRIVERS custom_vr)
11 endif()
```

Listing 4: This block of CMake instructions creates a new library for the project. All files within the directory are included in the build target, which can later be linked into other targets. Additionally, the xrt-interface library is linked to the target to enable integration with Monado’s interface system.

There is also a special function to get the camera in a tracked pose. This function retrieves the position from the historical buffer, which stores the headset’s positions at specific times, and can interpolate between them. This functionality will not be used, as we see later, as we will overwrite this functionality with the RealSense device driver.

As a final step, the entire library must be added as a target in the CMake configuration. This begins with adding a new CMake parameter to the root CMake file, which enables or disables the build process for the custom VR headset driver. However, to fully integrate the build, a corresponding build target must be defined in a separate file.

Within the drivers directory, there is a dedicated CMake file responsible for building all driver libraries. To add the new target, the instructions shown in Listing 4 are followed. This build process is conditional, controlled by the newly added CMake setting. When this setting is enabled, the variable `XRT_BUILD_DRIVER_CUSTOM_VR` is evaluated to true and the build target is included.

The target compiles all source files required for the driver (see Lines 2–7) and links against the xrt-interface library to provide access to the interfaces used by Monado (see Lines 8–9). In line 10, the driver’s name is appended to the list of enabled drivers, ensuring that debug output for the driver is included in the CMake project.

5.2.2 Enable VI-SLAM system on Windows

To enable movement, the device must track its own position. Fortunately, Monado already has a system in place that allows a VI-SLAM system to be loaded, enabling tracking functionality. However, the starting point is actually the RealSense camera driver, which already exists. This driver supports two different tracking modes. One mode allows the camera itself to track its position and send it to the runtime, as is the case with the RealSense TM2. The other mode allows the host system, meaning the runtime, to receive

the IMU and image data, enabling it to perform the tracking itself. In this project, the latter option is used, as the RealSense D415i does not support onboard tracking. However, the VI-SLAM system was disabled on Windows due to compatibility issues. To address this, a new CMake option called **XRT_FEATURE_SLAM_WIN** was added to enable SLAM tracking on Windows. This flag was also added to the checks in the RealSense driver to enable tracking initialization. Additionally, the new option was included in places where the Linux SLAM flag was used, allowing full support.

The next challenge was overcoming the incompatibility of Linux-specific function calls used to load dynamic libraries. On Linux, `.so` files, which are shared object libraries, are loaded using the `dlopen` function to retrieve a handle to the library, and `dlsym` to retrieve a function from the library based on its name. To test whether the system could correctly load a DLL on Windows, a new project was created that simply implements the VIT interface. This interface serves as the mounting point for the library as defined in Monado. The new project consisted only of the implementation of the VIT interface and its definition. However, to get the library working on Windows, the function definitions in the VIT interface needed to be adapted to include the `__declspec(dllexport)` attribute, otherwise the functions would not be accessible after compilation. This project was also intended to serve as a wrapper library, allowing the integration of alternative tracking software that does not directly implement the interface. In this role, it provides a place where glue code can be written.

The next step was to inform the runtime of the library's location. This is done by setting the **VIT_SYSTEM_LIBRARY_PATH** environment variable to the appropriate DLL path. With that in place, the system could be tested to check whether the library is accepted.

To replace the Linux-specific functions, Windows equivalents were needed. After some research, the corresponding functions were identified: **LoadLibrary** for loading the DLL from a given path, and **GetProcAddress** for retrieving function pointers. However, the handle returned by **LoadLibrary** is of type **HINSTANCE**, not `void*` as in Linux. To resolve this, a platform-dependent type definition was written that selects the correct

```

1     #ifdef XRT_OS_WINDOWS
2         #include <windows.h>
3         #define LIBTYPE HINSTANCE
4         #define CLOSELIB(lib) FreeLibrary((lib))
5     #elif defined(XRT_OS_LINUX) || defined(XRT_OS_ANDROID)
6         #define LIBTYPE void*
7         #define CLOSELIB(lib) dlclose((lib))
8     #endif

```

Listing 5: This definition sets the type for the library handle and the corresponding function to release it, depending on the operating system.

```

1  #elif defined(XRT_OS_WINDOWS)
2      vit->handle=LoadLibrary(path);
3      if (vit->handle == NULL) {
4          DWORD err = GetLastError();
5          U_LOG_E("Failed to open VIT library: %lu",err);
6          return false;
7      }
8  #else

```

Listing 6: In this definition, the loading of the library is done by using the "LoadLibrary" function with the path of the file as an argument. This returns a handle that gets stored in the visual inertial tracking object.

handle type depending on the operating system. This can be seen in the Listing 5. Another change that needed to be addressed was error handling. In Linux, an error code is returned from the function, which is checked to determine whether the operation was successful. If it was not, an error is logged and the function returns. In Windows, the process is slightly different. When an error occurs in one of the functions, the returned handle is NULL. This indicates that something went wrong, but to retrieve the actual error code, a function called **GetLastError** must be called. This function returns the error code as a **DWORD**, which can then be used to determine the cause of the failure. The final implementation can be seen in Listing 6 and 7.

As a final step, some feature-specific code was already implemented in the setup of the SLAM UI. Therefore, directive **#ifdef** was used to filter out feature-dependent code. With that in place, the interface could now be tested using some log output, which is triggered when the interface is accessed. This concludes the process of loading and accessing the VI-SLAM library on Windows in Monado.

```

1  #elif defined(XRT_OS_WINDOWS)
2      FARPROC proc = GetProcAddress(handle, name);
3      if (proc == NULL) {
4          DWORD err = GetLastError();
5          U_LOG_E("Failed to load symbol on
6                  windows: %s %lu", name, err);
7          return false;
8      }
9      *proc_ptr = proc;
10     return true;
11 #elses

```

Listing 7: Here, an individual function can be retrieved from the library with the **GetProcAddress**. A function pointer can be retrieved by giving the function the handle to the function and the name of the function.

5.2.3 Building a VI-SLAM library on Windows

Now that the runtime supports loading the interface, a VI-SLAM library must be built on Windows to generate a DLL that the system can load and interact with. There are many different libraries and methods available that implement some form of visual-inertial tracking. After several failed attempts with different libraries, ORB-SLAM3 showed promising progress during the compilation process.

After running CMake on the project for the first time, many errors occurred, most of which were compiler-related. MSVC does not recognize many build flags used by the Linux compiler. This led to the removal of several CMake definition lines and the deletion or replacement of flags that MSVC could not interpret.

There were also some dependency issues involving multiple libraries. Some of them were built directly in the project, for example, DBoW2, which implements a hierarchical bag-of-words approach to find similar images. Other applications were expected to be installed on the system, such as the RealSense library, which enables access to the RealSense cameras.

Some of these issues were resolved by changing the file extension from `.so` to `.dll`. Other problems were resolved by installing missing dependencies or successfully compiling the required projects. After addressing all errors, the system generated the CMake files needed to build the entire project.

The next step was to build the system. As expected, this resulted in additional errors. Due to the difference in operating systems, the `usleep()` function was not defined. Additionally, the C interface of the library had to include the `__declspec(dllexport)` attribute for its exported functions. There were further issues that needed to be fixed, but in the end the system successfully built the DLL file.

Unfortunately, when testing it in the wrapper library, it did not work due to a bug in the code, likely caused by compiler differences. The exact cause of the failure was not further investigated and the ORB-SLAM3 project was ultimately not used. This process of fixing the compilation and then encountering a major roadblock happened multiple times.

Ultimately, the Basalt library was utilized, which is also recommended by the creators of monado. Fortunately, Basalt implements the VIT interface, making the previously self-written wrapper library obsolete. As in the previously described build, the first step was to fix the project's CMake files. The C++ standard was set to C++20 to ensure that all required language features and standard library classes are available. Additionally, the compiler flag `/bigobj` was added to increase the maximum number of sections in an object file from 2^{16} (65,536) to a higher limit, thereby avoiding compilation errors. Next, several lines in the build configuration had to be adjusted because they included parameters not supported by MSVC. For example, the `-O3` flag used in Linux enables more aggressive optimizations than `-O2`, but it is not available in the Windows compiler and causes an error. To resolve this, `-O3` was replaced with `/O2`, ensuring that the compiler would still

optimize the code.

To manage dependencies, the VCPKG package manager was integrated into the project. This allowed all required libraries to be automatically installed and correctly located by CMake. Additional dependencies were included in a third-party directory containing projects that are also built as part of the root Basalt project. After resolving these issues, CMake successfully generated the required build files.

However, during the build process, additional issues arose. One minor problem was the redundant use of the template keyword on non-template objects. For example: `Q2Jp.template block(start_idx, 0, poses_size, poses_size)` In this case, the variable does not require the template keyword. Simply removing it in multiple instances resolved the compilation errors.

Another issue involved undefined macros that were expected to be provided by the standard library. One such case was the missing definition for the maximum float value, typically referred to as `MAXFLOAT`. A macro named `FLT_MAX` already has this value, so the line `#define MAXFLOAT FLT_MAX` was sufficient to fix the problem.

Additionally, the type `SIZE_T` was undefined. This was resolved by adding a typedef, defining `SIZE_T` as an alias for `size_t`.

It also became evident that MSVC is stricter with implicit casts, so several of these had to be replaced with `static_cast` to prevent compilation errors.

Another issue related to standard library differences was a name collision. A class implemented two functions named `min` and `max`, which conflicted with macros of the same name defined in the standard library. This resulted in confusing error messages that stated that the `min` and `max` functions declared in the header file were undefined. The solution was to `#undef` the `min` and `max` macros in that file, which resolved the conflict.

In one particular file, the Anonymous Pro font was used by defining a constant variable that was supposed to hold the binary data from a separate C header file. However, this file was missing from the repository. The font had to be downloaded manually from Google Fonts. Since no code was available to load a `.ttf` file directly, the entire binary content had to be transferred to a C header file. To achieve this, the `xxd` command was used to convert the binary `.ttf` file into the target file format. This process creates a large array that contains the binary data of the font as a `const unsigned char` variable. The command

```
1 xxd -i AnonymousPro.ttf > AnonymousPro.inc

1 extern "C" const unsigned char AnonymousPro_ttf[] = {
2     0x00, 0x01, 0x00, 0x00, ...}
3 unsigned int AnonymousPro_ttf_len = 112280;
```

Listing 8: `xxd` is used to create a hexdump of any file. In this case, it converts the font into a C header file containing the binary data. The `-i` flag enables C-style array output. On the bottom, we can see the definition and size of the array.

used for the conversion is shown in Listing 8.

The resulting header file was then included in the appropriate namespace, resolving the font-related issue.

The final failure point involved the export of the VIT interface. As mentioned previously, exporting functions in a DLL requires explicit marking. Once all relevant functions were marked correctly for export, the entire compilation process was completed successfully and Monado was able to load the DLL and instantiate a tracking object.

5.2.4 Adaptation of the RealSense Driver

In Monado, a driver for detecting and registering a new RealSense camera was already implemented. The implementation is split into two different modes. One in which the host system calculates the pose and one in which the camera itself returns tracked positions. In this implementation, the first system was used. Fortunately, the implementation was fairly general, making the integration of the camera straightforward. However, some default parameters needed to be adjusted. These values are shown in Listing 9.

A notable parameter appears in line 2, where the camera's video format is set to **RS2_FORMAT_Y8**. This indicates that the stream delivers an 8-bit grayscale image, which can be retrieved from the streams defined by the indices in lines 16 and 17. Additionally, in line 15, the stream type is set to the infrared camera, which aligns with the default video format specified for the RealSense device.

```

1  #define DEFAULT_STEREO                true
2  #define DEFAULT_XRT_VIDEO_FORMAT     XRT_FORMAT_L8
3  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_FORMAT        RS2_FORMAT_Y8
4  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_WIDTH         848
5  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_HEIGHT        480
6  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_FPS           30
7  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_CHANGE_EXPOSURE true
8  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_AUTOEXPOSURE  false
9  #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_EXPOSURE      33000
10 #define DEFAULT_VIDEO_GAIN           16
11 // IMU Settings
12 #define DEFAULT_GYRO_FPS              200
13 #define DEFAULT_ACCEL_FPS             200
14 // Stereo Stream settings
15 #define DEFAULT_STREAM_TYPE           RS2_STREAM_INFRARED
16 #define DEFAULT_STREAM1_INDEX        1
17 #define DEFAULT_STREAM2_INDEX        2

```

Listing 9: In the camera driver, the default values were targeted towards the RealSense D455. The default parameters did not coincide with the D435i therefore the parameters have been replaced with the needed default values.

The default frequency for both the gyroscope and the accelerometer is set to 200 Hz. This value is specifically chosen on the basis of the camera’s capabilities. Similarly, the resolution was set to 848×480 at 30 frames per second. Like the IMU frequency, these values are selected according to the camera’s supported specifications.

In order for Monado to correctly interpret and handle the incoming data, a video format must be specified using a Monado-specific format type. In line 2, the format is set to **XRT_FORMAT_L8**, which defines an 8-bit luminance channel. This format is interpreted as an RGB image where each pixel has the same value across all color channels. By aligning the camera’s video format with Monado’s expected format, the system can correctly process the incoming data.

All other parameters, such as gain and exposure, were adjusted using the RealSense Viewer. This tool allows live parameter tuning while observing the camera stream. Through trial and error, appropriate values for gain and exposure were determined.

Another change was the acceptance of the Windows Slam Tracking system. This change involved the addition of the **XRT_SLAM_WINDOWS** to the check prior to instantiation of the slam system.

As a final step, the function responsible for creating a driver instance was exposed in the driver’s library. This function is typically used by the auto-prober, which detects new devices and creates the corresponding instances.

5.2.5 Implementing the Target Builder

Now that the device driver has been written, the RealSense driver has been adapted, and the SLAM library has been integrated, the final implementation step in Monado can be completed. This involves adding a new file named *target_builder_custom_vr.c* to the *src/xrt/targets/common* directory. The entire system for creating a new device in Monado is built around a builder pattern. This approach enables modularity and extensibility, allowing for the support of a wide range of devices.

To inform the program about how to create the VR device, the function **t_builder_custom_vr_create** must be defined. This function is responsible for returning a preconfigured builder object that is then used to instantiate the device. Additionally, the function must be registered in the **target_list** variable and wrapped in a **#ifdef** block to prevent compilation errors when the corresponding CMake flag is not set and the driver is not included in the build. The builder function is seen in Listing 10. This code block defines the builder function. In line 3, the builder struct is instantiated. Line 5 sets the function responsible for estimating the system components, allowing Monado to know the features of the device without opening it. In line 6, the function for opening the device is assigned, while line 7 sets the function for destroying the device instance. Lines 8–11 define several metadata fields that can be printed when using the CLI. Line 12 provides the option to exclude the device from automatic discovery through an environment variable. Finally, line 15 implements the actual

```

1  struct xrt_builder* t_builder_custom_vr_create(void)
2  {
3      struct u_builder *ub = U_TYPED_CALLOC(struct u_builder);
4
5      ub->base.estimate_system = custom_vr_estimate_system;
6      ub->base.open_system = u_builder_open_system_static_roles;
7      ub->base.destroy = custom_vr_destroy;
8      ub->base.identifier = "custom_vr";
9      ub->base.name = "Custom VR devices builder";
10     ub->base.driver_identifiers = driver_list;
11     ub->base.driver_identifier_count = ARRAY_SIZE(driver_list);
12     ub->base.exclude_from_automatic_discovery =
13         !debug_get_bool_option_enable_custom_vr();
14
15     ub->open_system_static_roles = custom_vr_open_system_impl;
16
17     return &ub->base;
18 }

```

Listing 10: These lines of code define the fields for the XR device builder. First, the builder object is instantiated. Then, the functions for offline feature estimation, device opening, and builder destruction are assigned. Following that, several debug fields are defined to provide useful information during runtime. The last two fields handle exclusion from automatic device discovery and specify the function responsible for instantiating the actual XR device.

instantiation of the device. This function is implicitly called by **open_system**. The function **custom_vr_open_system_impl** is responsible for creating the device instance. In Listing 11, the most important lines are shown. In line 1, the custom VR headset instance is generated. The called function is implemented in *sample_hmd.c*. In line 2, the SLAM device, specifically, the RealSense driver, is instantiated with a prober attached

```

1  struct xrt_device cv_device = custom_vr_create();
2  struct xrt_device slam_device = create_tracked_rs_device(xp);
3  struct xrt_device head_wrap = multi_create_tracking_override(
4      XRT_TRACKING_OVERRIDE_DIRECT,
5      cv_device, slam_device,
6      XRT_INPUT_GENERIC_HEAD_POSE,
7      &head_offset);
8  ubrh->head = head_wrap;

```

Listing 11: These lines of code combine two XR devices in order to apply tracking to the custom VR headset. First, the custom VR device and the tracking device are instantiated. Second, the tracking functionality of the custom VR device gets overwritten with the tracking device. Then, the resulting object is assigned to the desired role.

that can detect whether the device is connected. The RealSense implementation library exposes this function. To combine the tracking capabilities of the RealSense driver with the functionality of the custom VR headset, the function in line 3 is called. It is responsible for overriding the necessary function pointers of the custom VR device to enable external tracking integration and ensure that both systems work seamlessly.

In line 4, the parameter for directly overwriting the headset's tracking is set. There is also an alternative mode in which the system enters an "attached" state, allowing the internal tracking of the VR headset to coexist with the RealSense tracking. However, this is not the case here, so the direct overwrite method is used. Line 5 specifies both the base device to be overridden and the SLAM device that provides the tracking. Line 6 defines the pose type as a head, and in line 7, the positional offset to the user's head is passed to the function. This call creates a new device that combines both visual and tracking components, which is then assigned as the head device on line 8.

The final functionality that was implemented in the builder is the definition of the offline feature estimation. This is shown in Listing 12. In lines 1 and 2, the expectation that a head-mounted device will be present is explicitly defined, and the maybe flag is also set to true.

Lines 4 to 7 specify that hand tracking will not be available. Lines 9 to 12 determine whether 6 Degrees of Freedom (6DoF) tracking will be supported. This depends on whether the RealSense D435i is connected to the computer. The function call on line 9 checks for the presence of the device by verifying whether any connected device matches the predefined Product ID (PID) and Vendor ID (VID). These values are 0x8086 for the VID and 0x0B3A for the PID. They are defined as macros in the implementation of the RealSense driver.

```
1 estimate->maybe.head = true;
2 estimate->certain.head = true;
3
4 estimate->certain.left = false;
5 estimate->certain.right = false;
6 estimate->maybe.left = false;
7 estimate->maybe.right = false;
8
9 estimate->certain.dof6 = u_builder_find_prober_device(
10     xpdevs, xpdev_count,
11     REALSENSE_D435I_VID, REALSENSE_D435I_PID,
12     XRT_BUS_TYPE_USB);
```

Listing 12: This code defines the expected features for the device. The presence of a head is certain, while hand tracking is not supported. The most notable feature is 6DoF tracking, which is only enabled if a RealSense camera is detected using the predefined PID and VID.

5.2.6 Unity Project Setup

Figure 5.6: In this image, we can see the Unity project. It consists of multiple objects that are necessary for the OpenXR integration and platform, with cubes on top to gain a sense of space when using it.

With the system up and running and the SLAM system ready to track the position, a test application can be built. Fortunately, utilizing the OpenXR standard makes this a well-documented task. For this test, a Unity project was set up because it provides full control over the scene, which can be beneficial since some applications restrict access to certain areas, leading to a more challenging tracking of bugs.

To start a new application, a new Unity project was generated with the standard 3D project template. After project creation is complete, the XR management plugin can be installed, a package that provides simple management for XR plug-ins. It handles loading, initialization, and settings, and it also offers build support for XR-related components. After installation, new options are available. For the test, a new desktop application was used, therefore, the checkbox for OpenXR was ticked in the desktop section.

This installed the plugin for OpenXR compatibility and changed the input system. Afterward, a restart of the project was necessary. After restart, the project identifies certain issues raised by the OpenXR system. Fortunately, Unity has a project validation feature that can automatically fix the issues. Only one issue was not fixable by the system, that was the selection of the interaction profile. This sets the bindings for a specific controller type, for example, an Oculus or an HTC Vive controller. In this project, this would not be necessary because we do not have a controller. However, for completeness, the "Khronos Simple controller" was added because this name best aligns with the OpenXR

Figure 5.7: This window shows the rendered scene for each eye.

theme.

To access the necessary components in the editor, the package "XR Interaction Toolkit" must be installed in Unity's package manager. This installation includes components that interact with the OpenXR system. The project is now configured to support OpenXR, but it still requires the components to be instantiated and configured in Unity.

To create a camera for rendering, a new XR Origin component was created. This component represents the player and holds the interaction with the OpenXR system for the head.

With this setup, the project can be started. Through the OpenXR load, the system can locate the OpenXR runtime and register the application with it. Monado is currently configured to open a window that corresponds to the resolution of the displays. The resulting unity project can be seen in Figure 5.6resulting image can be seen in Figure 5.7.

5.2.7 Display writeout

This window, as seen in Figure 5.7, is a single window, which is not what we wanted because we have two displays. In Linux, this problem would be easily solved. The tool `xrandr` can be used to software-fuse two displays, making them appear as one large display. Monado can then use this display to display the rendering in fullscreen. This would be the full-screen approach.

There is also a technology called Nvidia Direct Mode, which can directly display the

rendered content onto displays, saving performance by reducing copying and transfer operations. This would also improve the device's latency. But with the limitation of having two separate displays, this kind of rendering is not possible. This means that Monado needs to supply two different windows and support direct mode for two displays simultaneously.

Unfortunately, Monado is built in such a way that adding another window with its own swapchain and window management is not a trivial task. After some trial and error, no significant progress could be made, leading to the conclusion that knowledge and experience in programming real-time rendering pipelines were insufficient. This leads to the option of an exterior solution. In general, there were two options: one was to copy the contents of the window and display them in two separate windows. The other was to adjust the displays in the virtual display space. This means that we place the two displays side by side and move the window over both displays.

In the following subsections, the implementation details are shown.

5.2.7.1 Copying the Output

The idea behind this approach was to use a virtual display to render both views in full screen. This full view can then be copied, and Windows recognizes the display screens built into the device.

To achieve this, virtual display driver (VDD) [51] was downloaded and installed. As the name suggests, this driver allows the creation of a new virtual screen that can be freely configured. In this case, the resolution of the virtual display was set to match the height and double the width of one of the built-in panels.

Once Windows recognized the display, an environment variable was set before launching Monado. This variable ensured that the rendered full-screen view would be shown on the virtual display. With that in place, it became possible to capture the image data directly from the screen.

In Listing 13, the memory setup for the screen grabber is shown. To keep the copy process efficient and reduce unnecessary data movements, the system was configured to perform only one copy operation per screen refresh. This helps reduce latency, which is critical in a real-time system like this.

In the first line, a handle is retrieved for the entire screen. To map the captured screen content directly into an OpenCV Matrix object, a Device Independent Bitmap (DIB) section is utilized. This section returns a pointer to the allocated memory. But before the DIB section can be created, a **BITMAPINFO** object must be set up. This is done between lines 3 and 12.

The most notable attributes in the definition are the height and the bit count. To capture the screen starting from the top, the height is set as a negative value. This inverts the image vertically, so the top of the screen matches the top of the image buffer. The bit count is set to 24, which means that only the red, green, and blue channels are used. In this case, no alpha channel is needed.

```

1  HDC hdcScreen = GetDC(NULL);
2
3  BITMAPINFOHEADER bi = {};
4  bi.biSize = sizeof(bi);
5  bi.biWidth = width;
6  bi.biHeight = -height;
7  bi.biPlanes = 1;
8  bi.biBitCount = 24;
9  bi.biCompression = BI_RGB;
10
11 BITMAPINFO binfo = {};
12 binfo.bmiHeader = bi;
13
14 void *pBits = nullptr;
15 HBITMAP hDib = CreateDIBSection(hdcScreen, &binfo,
16 DIB_RGB_COLORS, &pBits, NULL, 0);
17
18 HDC hMem = CreateCompatibleDC(hdcScreen);
19 SelectObject(hMem, hDib);
20
21 int stride = ((width*3 + 3) & ~3);
22 cv::Mat screen_mat(height,width,CV_8UC3, pBits, stride );
23

```

Listing 13: In this code block, the memory for the copy process is prepared. In the first line, the handle for the screen is retrieved. To perform the copy operation, a Device Independent Bitmap (DIB) is used, which requires a bitmap definition. This definition is created from line 3 to line 12. After that, the DIB section is created and connected to the device memory (lines 15–19). In the final two lines, the stride is set, and the OpenCV Matri is instantiated with a pointer to the allocated memory.

After the info object is prepared, the DIB section is created in lines 15 and 16. It uses the `hdcScreen` and the `binfo` structure to define the memory layout. The value `DIB_RGB_COLORS` specifies that the memory should store RGB values. The `NULL` argument indicates that the memory should be stored in system RAM, making it fast and easy to access for subsequent processing. The last zero defines the offset in memory, which is none. To access the memory, the function call writes the memory address into the `pBits` variable.

Now that there is a CPU-side memory that can be accessed, a new memory handle gets initialized for the screen device. Afterwards, the DIB is selected into the memory context, which ensures that any copy operation is directed to the DIB.

Because the rows of the copied memory are aligned in multiples of 4, OpenCV’s matrix needs to be aware of this and act accordingly. This behavior can be set in the constructor of the matrix by specifying the last value. The stride variable gets set to the nearest

```
1 BitBlt(  
2     hMem,  
3     0, 0,  
4     width,height,  
5     hdcScreen,  
6     x, y,  
7     SRCCOPY  
8 );
```

Listing 14: This line of code copies the data from one buffer to another. In line 2 the handle for the target memory is defined. Lines 3 and 4 define the target area. 5 and 6 define the source from which the data is coming, and line 7 defines the operation.

up-rounded multiple of four (see Line 21).

By using the pBits memory address as a data source and the previously calculated stride to construct the matrix, the memory from the DIB is now mapped to the matrix. This concludes the setup for the memory.

In Listing 14, the operation of the copy process is displayed. It is accomplished using the **BitBlt** operation, which is essentially a block copy operation where the source and target locations are specified. Line 2 defines the target memory, which is the DIB. Line 3 is responsible for providing the target location in the target memory, and line 4 represents the size of the block. In line 5, we define the target device with the source location in line 6. The last parameter on line 7 specifies that the whole data gets copied to the target memory.

With this in place, we only need to define two regions of interest in OpenCV, which cover half the image. These operations also do not copy anything. The last step of the process is to display the images using the **imshow** function of OpenCV.

This results in two separate windows which can be displayed in full screen on each display.

5.2.7.2 Using Window Management

To achieve minimal latency, the window must be displayed directly on the screen without any intermediate processing. With only one window available, this can only be done by stretching the rendered window across both screens. To automate this process, a Python script was written to ensure that the window is placed correctly.

In Listing 15, the code for the window-moving process is shown. The window is retrieved using its title in line 1. Lines 3–5 select the monitors that are part of the headset, assuming that they are already arranged side by side, with each display corresponding to one eye. The width of the window is then set to the combined width of both screens, while the height is set to the height of one display. It is assumed that both displays are the same height. In the last line, the window is moved to the upper left corner of the virtual

```
1 window = gw.getWindowsWithTitle(window_title)[0]
2
3 monitors = get_monitors()
4 monitor1 = monitors[monitor_index_left]
5 monitor2 = monitors[monitor_index_right]
6
7 combined_width = monitor1.width + monitor2.width
8 window.resizeTo(combined_width, monitor1.height)
9
10 window.moveTo(monitor1.x, monitor1.y)
11
```

Listing 15: This code moves a window to the left upper corner of a display and stretches it across the left and the right eye.

screen space, which completes the script.

With this setup, there is no need for a separate copy process. This results in a significant improvement over the previous method, as it helps to reduce latency.

5.3 Discussion

In this section, the software implementation is discussed. Starting with a summary of what was done and the overall goals, further on, a comparison between the first implementation and the second implementation with Monado is presented. Furthermore, the two methods for displaying the rendered panel from Monado onto the headset are also discussed and evaluated against each other.

5.3.1 Summary

The goal of this chapter is to create software that can track a camera's position visually. This positional data should then be transferred to Unity, where it can be applied to the user view.

The first approach to the software project involved using an RGB-D camera in conjunction with a custom Python script to estimate the position of the camera. The Intel RealSense D435i was chosen because, compared to other RGB-D cameras, it offered the most balanced set of features. Important factors in this decision were the weight of the device, its resolution, and its framerate. Another advantage was the availability of an easy-to-integrate Python library, which included a built-in frame alignment function. This made it possible to directly use the provided package without having to implement the alignment process from scratch.

These images could then be used to estimate the camera's pose. This resulted in the need for a library that could estimate the relative movement between two frames. For

this, Open3D was chosen, as it provided exactly this functionality without the need for much frame modification.

In order to send the data to Unity, a transportation method was chosen. MQTT was selected because it does not require knowledge of who is sending or receiving. The only dependency is on a broker that needs to run. The script publishes the data as JSON to a predefined topic, to which Unity can subscribe. To connect Unity to the MQTT broker, a NuGet package called MQTTnet was installed, as it provides the needed functionality and is well-documented. When a message is received, the MQTT client calls a callback function. However, this callback does not run on the Unity main thread. This causes problems when updating the pose of an object directly inside the callback. To solve this, the function call is dispatched to the main thread utilizing a queue that holds all function calls and the Update function, which processes all functions within the queue. With this change, the data can be processed further within Unity. Inside Unity, the transformation data can be applied to both cameras, with each of them responsible for one eye. With this, a working prototype was completed.

Because this project does not use any form of standardization or existing communication methods already used by other software projects, the implementation is highly specific and useful only if a developer builds their project with this VR implementation in mind. Pre-existing software, such as VR games on Steam, cannot be used because they are not integrated with this system. This led to the idea of using OpenXR as a standardized method of communication with other programs, making the project more accessible for existing VR applications. With this in mind, Monado was used, an open-source OpenXR runtime. In order to increase accessibility for users, the whole project was brought over to Windows.

Because Monado is written in C/C++, the previous solution was discarded. By targeting Windows as the host operating system, multiple difficulties arose. To compile the project, the source code needed to be adapted in order to overcome the differences in compilers when comparing it to gcc.

For positional tracking, an SLAM interface was already implemented in the project, but an adaptation was required for library loading in the Windows build. With the interface ready to use, the Basalt library was compiled on Windows. By adjusting various build parameters and modifying compiler-specific definitions in the source code, a shared library was compiled with the required interface functions. This library can then be loaded into Monado by defining an environment variable that holds the path to Basalt at startup.

However, the SLAM system would not function without camera data. Fortunately, a RealSense library integration already existed as a separate driver. By adjusting the parameters for the D435i camera and making minor changes to the existing source code, most of the implementation could be reused.

In the end, a custom target builder was created, which contains the instantiation code for the custom VR device and the glue code for integrating other drivers. It also defines the expected features of the device. By overriding the tracking function of the custom VR

headset driver with that of the RealSense driver, the headset was able to track its position and send it to Unity using the OpenXR specification.

Fortunately, Unity includes an integrated package manager, which also provides an existing OpenXR package with all the necessary implementations. The project can be set up to use this functionality with its camera system. When starting the runtime and an OpenXR application, the rendered views are placed side by side in a separate window. Because Monado only supports fullscreen on a single display and not two separate ones, two alternative solutions were implemented to render the views on the separate monitors of the headset.

The first solution creates a new virtual display, renders the view in full screen onto it, copies the display's content, and renders it again on the separate screens. The second solution moves and resizes the window across both displays, which requires the monitors to be configured side by side. With these solutions, it is now possible to display rendered views on the headset's screens.

5.3.2 Evaluation of Implementations

In this chapter, two methods for implementing software for a VR headset are described. One with a custom approach, where the transfer method for tracked data is sent over MQTT, and another one where an OpenXR runtime is used to leverage the accessibility of the Standardization. Furthermore, for the rendered window implemented by Monado, it displays both views side-by-side, but the screens are individually separated in the OS, which means that there needs to be some kind of workaround or additional implementation.

5.3.2.1 Custom vs. Standardised

Comparing the two implementations, the custom solution has significantly less overhead in terms of source code. No standard needs to be met, which reduces complexity and avoids additional lines of code. Using a fixed camera, a fixed library, and letting Unity handle all rendering and display tasks, the script stays simple. Monado, on the other hand, is a much more complex project. It not only provides positional data, but also needs to supply rendering targets, handle window and display rendering, driver management, integration of multiple graphics APIs, and other features to comply with the OpenXR specification.

However, because Monado is an OpenXR conformant, it can run applications that were not specifically developed for this project. It can act as a runtime for many existing applications already on the market. VR developers do not need to worry about the interface between their program and Monado, as this is already defined by the standard. This is a major advantage compared to the custom approach, which does not offer such functionality. Developers of each VR application would need to manually include the setup for the MQTT connection. This adds complexity to the Unity project, reduces maintainability, and increases the risk of bugs due to unforeseen side effects after the integration. This means that the custom solution is only feasible in specialized scenarios

where specific features are required and where the Unity project can be built around the integration with the headset.

Because of the simplicity of the custom solution, special features can be integrated more easily. Managing a few lines of code is much simpler than working with a project that has several thousand, because it reduces the chances of bugs and lowers the maintenance effort for the developer. However, this also means that all the features must be implemented manually. In *Monado*, some features are already available. For example, distortion correction is included. The driver class provides functions to define distortion parameters, which are then used to calculate the undistorted view. In addition, existing drivers can be used without having to write new driver code, making it easier to reuse and build on existing functionality.

In the end, it comes down to what the headset is used for. In scenarios where highly specialized features need to be implemented, a custom solution can reduce development time and offer a more flexible integration with different technologies. On the other hand, the *OpenXR* runtime provides a more industrialized approach with a defined interface, allowing it to be used with a wider range of applications.

5.3.2.2 Display Copy vs. Window Mapping

In the last part of the *OpenXR* implementation, an obstacle occurred where two views are displayed onto one rendered window side-by-side, which does not allow the views to be displayed onto the screens independently.

The display copy approach used two windows that were then displayed full screen on each display. This meant that each display could render the view in exclusive mode, which allowed them to access the screen memory directly without needing to respect the draw calls of other windows, thereby improving performance slightly. This is a feature of fullscreen optimization on Windows [52]. In comparison, the windowed approach uses the render window and resizes it across both screens, making it not possible to use it in full-screen, making full-screen optimization not possible.

A downside of copying the screen is, as the name suggests, the copying process itself, which takes additional time. On average, this adds a latency of 14 ms to the existing tracking and rendering latency of *Monado*. The windowed approach, on the other hand, adds zero additional latency. It renders the views directly onto the screens without any intermediate steps, making it a much more performant solution.

However, the downside is the setup required. Both screens need to be placed side by side in the Windows display manager, otherwise, the system breaks. But the other solution also requires an extra step. Installing a virtual display driver can cause issues if not configured correctly. In practice, it seems easier to misconfigure the virtual display than to incorrectly arrange the screens in the display manager.

In general, the window mapping solution is preferred as the latency overhead of the copying approach far outweighs the benefits of full-screen rendering. The windowed so-

lution provides lower latency, better performance, and a more responsive experience in general. In addition, the setup process is simpler and more reliable, making it easier to use and less prone to errors compared to configuring a virtual display for screen copying.

Building a VR Headset

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6.4	Configuring Environment	66

This chapter provides instructions for creating the custom VR headset described in the previous chapters. It begins by listing the required parts for each assembly step and provides detailed instructions for building the hardware. A description of the compilation process for Monado follows this. Since Monado does not run as expected by simply starting the program, the necessary environment variables are listed, along with a detailed explanation of the user interface, allowing for custom modifications if needed. Finally, if game support via SteamVR is desired, this chapter also includes an explanation of the required modifications.

6.1 Assembling the Headset

To create a new headset, a 3D printer, a Metal Saw, a lighter, or other source of heat, and a soldering iron are required. In Table 6.1, the parts that need to be purchased are listed. For 3D printing, a total of 39 parts need to be printed, 10 for each eye module, 8 for the case, and 1 for the electronics compartment. The assembly process is divided into two parts. The first describes the construction of the left eye module, which can also be used for the right eye module. For the second part, the full assembly of the case with the eye modules and the electronic compartment is described.

PartN	Count	Product ID
Threaded Rod M3 55mm	4	B0D5DGMXNN (Amazon)
Press Insert M3	4	B0CRYWCYMG (Amazon)
Allen Screw M2 4mm	40	B0CKN2VK12 (Amazon)
Press Insert M2	41	B0CRYWCYMG (Amazon)
Allen Screw M2 6mm	1	B0CKN2VK12 (Amazon)
Display with Breackoutboard	2	1005008477815602 (AliExpress)
MIPI-to-HDMI Board	2	1005008477815602 (AliExpress)

Table 6.1: Components which need to be bought with their corresponding Product ID and vendor

6.1.1 Eye Module

In Table 6.2, the required parts for the headset are listed, and in Figure 6.1, the 3D printed parts are listed and enumerated. The first step is to prepare the threaded rods. Using a metal saw, cut a 3mm deep line in the center of the front side of the rod. This cut divides one end of the rod into two halves. Remove one half so that a 3 mm high semicircle remains, connected to the rest of the threaded rod. This semicircle is used to connect to part 5 and transfer the rotational movement from the gear to the threaded rod. By heating the cut end, the rod can be pressed into the semicircular hole in the center of part 5. The heated metal will slightly melt the plastic, allowing it to deform and form tightly around the metal for a secure fit. This process is done twice, once for each part 5. The press inserts can then be mounted on the 3D-printed parts. It is important to press them straight, otherwise the screws may sit crooked or, in the worst case, not fit at all. Parts 1 and 2 each require four M2 inserts, marked by small holes on the bottom and the side. Part 3 requires two M2 and two M3 inserts: M3 inserts for the threaded rods and M2 inserts for securing the breakout board. Part 8 requires six M2 inserts, three in the back for the MIPI-to-HDMI board, two to hold the side cover, and one in the top for the connection to the IPD mechanism.

With the preparations completed, the assembly can begin. First, the display is slid into the bracket in part 3 and the breakout board is mounted on the back (see Figure

Part	Count
3D Printed Parts	10
Threaded Rod M3 55mm	2
Press Insert M3	2
Allen Screw M2 4mm	15
Press Insert M2	16
Display with Breackoutboard	1
MIPI-to-HDMI Board	1

Table 6.2: Parts for one Eye module

Figure 6.1: 3D printed Parts for the eye module with an enumeration

4.8 a and b). The display and breakout board are then connected through the opening in part 3. Next, part 2 is prepared by placing the lens inside, and part 1 is placed on top of the lens. Part 2 must be positioned below part 1 because it has a small cutout to route the connection cable from the breakout board to the outside (see Figure 4.8 c). The prepared part 3 is then slid into parts 1 and 2 using the dovetail slides. The connection cable passes through the slit, and part 4 is mounted on the back of parts 1 and 2 to secure the assembly, using four screws. Now, screw both part 5 gears with the threaded rod into the two holes of part 4, which should align with the M3 insert in part 3. Now, screw the gears in until the gears sit flush on part 4. Also, make sure that part 3 is not tilted and is parallel to the lens. Now place part 6 on the middle bump of part 4, and one part 7 on the bump above. It should now look like Figure 4.8 d).

The parts of the surrounding shell are shown in Figure 6.1 b. This shell encloses the assembled module, blocks out external light, mounts the HDMI-to-MIPI board, and connects the module to the main case. This is the most challenging part of the assembly process. The goal is to achieve the construction shown in Figure 4.9 a.

First, part 10 is placed in the smaller compartment in the back of part 8 and secured through the hole with the second part 7 gear. The previously assembled module is then slid into the prepared part 8 with all gears already in place. During sliding, the cable must be routed through the opening on top of part 8. Once the module is almost fully inserted, there is a good chance that the part 7 gear holding part 10 will not align with the gears on part 4. By gently moving part 10 while pressing the assembly together, part 7 will engage correctly with the inner gear system.

Once aligned, the assembly is secured in place by inserting two screws into the top and bottom front of part 8, which are positioned directly above and below the lens. Then Part 9 is placed and screwed onto the side of the module, sealing the shell. At this stage,

Part	Count
3D Printed Parts	9
Allen Screw M2 4mm	10
Press Insert M2	9
Allen Screw M2 6mm	1

Table 6.3: Parts for one Eye module

the assembly should resemble Figure 4.9 b. For the final step, the HDMI-to-MIPI board is mounted to the back of the assembly, and the cable from the breakout board is connected. The completed module should now look as shown in Figure 4.9 c.

The eye module is now fully assembled and ready for use. To build the module for the opposite side, the same steps are followed, but the process is mirrored.

6.1.2 Case and Electronics Compartment

In Table 6.3, the required parts for the case are listed, and the required 3D printed parts are enumerated in Figure 6.2. As with previous assemblies, the first step is to prepare the parts for mounting. This means inserting all necessary threaded inserts before doing any other work. In this case, only part 11 requires threaded inserts. Four inserts are needed on each side to mount the side panels, and one insert is placed on top, centered on the bump. With this, the preparation for the case assembly is complete.

First, the two eye modules are inserted into the left and right sides of part 11. To secure them, the left and right panels (parts 12 and 13) are mounted on their respective sides. It is important to check that both modules can move freely and do not bind to the dovetail slides during adjustment.

Figure 6.2: 3D printed Parts for the case and the Electronics Compartment

For the IPD adjustment mechanism, part 17 is placed on top of the device. The higher side is inserted through the left hole and onto the top of the left eye module, where a hexagonal knob serves as the mounting point. The same process is repeated on the right side with part 18. Each connection point is secured with an $M2 \times 4$ mm screw. After moving both modules so that they meet in the center, part 14 is placed on the center bump at the top of the case, enabling synchronized movement of both modules by turning the gear. Next, part 15 is inserted and fixed using an $M2 \times 6$ mm screw, which is threaded into the prepared insert—this is the only step that uses a different screw size. Then, part 16 is screwed into part 14 so that, when tightened, it presses against part 15 and creates a friction joint. Because part 15 has a hexagonal connection point, it cannot rotate, which ensures that the entire IPD mechanism is locked in place. The mechanism should now look like Figure 4.10 a. Part 19 can be clipped on the backside of the device. It features two holes in which a camera can be mounted. The headset is now fully assembled and can be plugged into a PC with HDMI and USB cables.

6.2 Compiling Monado for Windows

The first challenge to overcome is compiling Monado for Windows. For this, the Visual Studio 2022 compiler (MSVC) and the CMake build system were installed and used. For dependency management, VCPKG should be used. It is a cross-platform package manager for C++ dependencies. Fortunately, VCPKG is fully integrated into the project, so CMake handles dependency management. The required dependencies for Windows are illustrated in Table 6.4.

With this in place, CMake successfully generates the project files, allowing the build process to begin. However, this leads to compilation errors, as the entire project was originally based on a Linux compiler. Unfortunately, the standard libraries differ slightly, which caused the initial compilation to fail due to `M_PI` being undefined. This issue can be

Dependencie name	Description
Eigen 3.x	linear algebra library
Pthreads Windows	POSIX threading header for Windows
SDL	access to mouse, keyboard, and other peripherals
Vulkan	Graphic API
HIDAPI	Bluetooth and USB interface
LibUSB	For USB device access
cJSON	JSON parser for C
WIL	For easier Windows development

Table 6.4: This Table lists the required dependencies for Monado along with a brief description of their general purpose. These dependencies must be installed to allow CMake to generate the necessary build files successfully.

Figure 6.3: This image shows the monado UI consisting of multiple windows.

quickly resolved by adding the line: `#define M_PI (3.14159265358979323846)`. After this addition, the compilation process completes successfully, and the system can be started for the first time.

6.3 Starting the System

By building and executing the "monado_service" target, the service can be started and used. However, at this stage, neither a device instance is created nor is the camera detected correctly. The reason for this is the absence of certain required environment variables (see Table 6.5).

The first variable is responsible for creating an instance of the custom VR device on startup. This is achieved by disabling automatic probing and implicitly registering the device in the system. The second variable is required for the RealSense driver. To correctly identify the connected cameras, the prober must be assigned a valid source index. Without this, the system crashes during startup due to missing stream configuration parameters.

For the SLAM library, two additional environment variables are necessary. One defines the path to the SLAM library, in this case the Basalt library. The other specifies the configuration file for the D435i. Basalt requires this configuration file to operate correctly, as it contains essential parameters such as camera intrinsics, resolution, IMU biases, standard deviations, and other calibration data. These values can be extracted from the camera itself using the RealSense camera calibration tool. For the IMU-specific statistical values, a pre-generated configuration file tailored for the D435i was used. The last envi-

Name	Value
CUSTOM_VR_ENABLE	1
RS_SOURCE_INDEX	0
SLAM_CONFIG	./d435i.toml
VIT_SYSTEM_LIBRARY_PATH	./basalt.dll
XRT_DEBUG_GUI	1

Table 6.5: Environment variables for starting monado properly. The first one is for instantiating the headset. Second for the streaming index of the camera, third and fourth for the slam configuration and the last one to enable the debug gui.

Environment variable enables the use of the debug GUI, shown in Figure 6.3. This interface was created using ImuGUI and provides controls and statistics for various features within Monado. Several windows within the UI are handy and have been frequently utilized during development.

One notable window is located in the bottom left corner. It serves as the control interface for the video source inside the RealSense driver. The top of the screen displays the real-time values from the gyroscope and accelerometer. A toggle button on the side enables a graph view that visualizes these sensor values over time. Below that, infrared images from the left and right cameras are shown.

In the top middle section, the RealSense Device window displays the status of the instantiated RealSense device. This window represents the RealSense driver implementation, which also handles the initialization of the SLAM instance. It provides real-time information about the currently tracked position and orientation of the device. Additionally, it allows configuration of translation and rotation offsets.

A notable detail is the label at the top of the window, which states "Tracked by: Host SLAM". This confirms that the tracking is handled by the external SLAM library, rather than assuming that the RealSense device is performing tracking on its own. This detail is important because if the system says that it is device-tracked, the whole tracking would not work. After all, the D435i does not support internal tracking.

On the right side, there is a large window with the title "SLAM Tracker #1". As the name suggests, this is the control window for the slam tracker. To start the whole slam tracking, the first checkbox needs to be ticked. This will start to route the data to the SLAM library. Right below, there is a reset button for resetting the tracker state. This is especially useful for debugging and testing the tracker when numerical instabilities occur.

Further down, the section for filtering of the signal is seen. For all filters, the predefined values were used. The first filter is the moving average filter. This filter takes the average over the predefined window and uses this value. The exponential smoothing filter smooths the data in a way that recent data is given more weight than older data. The last one, the one euro filter, is a low-pass filter with an adaptive threshold.

In the prediction section of the window, the current values of the accelerometer and

gyroscope are displayed. These values are received from the RealSense driver. Also, the constant value for the gravitational correction is adjustable from this window. But one of the most interesting settings is the "Prediction Type". In this dropdown menu, there are multiple options: "None", "Interpolate SLAM poses", "Also gyro", "Also accel", and "Latest IMU".

The "None" option disables the entire prediction system. "Interpolate SLAM poses" uses only the tracked poses from the SLAM system, and if intermediate poses are needed, the system interpolates between them. With "Also gyro" and "Also accel", the data from the gyroscope or accelerometer, respectively, are added to the evaluation pipeline. The "Latest IMU" option uses all available IMU data to retrieve the most accurate and up-to-date pose.

In the last section, we can see another preview of the received image frames which are processed by the SLAM system.

The middle bottom window, called "Compositor #1," can display useful information about the system's performance. A critical value is the current frame rate, expressed in frames per second (FPS). This indicates the number of images that Monado can process in one second. Further down, the chart illustrates the time it takes for a new frame to be fully rendered and displayed. The last two sections, "View[0]" and "View[1]" show the current rendered image if an OpenXR application is running.

6.4 Configuring Environment

To inform OpenXR runtime that our platform exists and that we intend to use it as our standard value, the registry must be edited. In `Computer\HKEY_LOCAL_MACHINE\SOFTWARE\Khronos\OpenXR\1` the path to the file `openxr_monado-dev.json` must be set. This file is generated during the application build and resides in the binaries directory. It has all the necessary values for the OpenXR loader to load an OpenXR application with the Monado runtime.

With this setup, it is possible to start VR programs from Unity, which then are displayed by Monado. For Steam gaming, there is a bit more setup involved. First of all, the Steam plugin needs to be compiled.

This is done by compiling the "driver_monado" target. This creates a new file in the `steamvr-monado/bin` including the `monado_driver.dll` which is the plugin for Steam. With this plugin, the driver now needs to be registered on Steam. This is done with a separate batch file that is shipped with the application. `./steam/steamapps/common/SteamVR/bin/vrpathreg.sh adddriver C:/path/to/dll/monado_driver.dll` let Steam know where the custom VR driver is. The success of the command can be verified by running `vrpathreg.sh` without any parameters. This enables the use of all hardware supported by Monado on Steam, but does not allow for playing games.

To enable game support, the OpenComposite application must be installed. It is responsible for forwarding the SteamVR calls to OpenXR. wBy starting the program and

clicking on the "Switch to OpenVR" button, the redirect is set in place. For the last step, a file in the game needs to be changed to work. Somewhere in the game directory, there is a file called *openvr_api.dll* . The OpenComposite repository provides a replacement file that needs to be swapped out in the game files. With this in place, Monado can be booted up, and then the game can start. This should now open the rendered window. The window can now be placed on top of the two displays to see the rendered view in the headset.

Conclusions and Future Work

7.1 Conclusion

In this thesis, a foundation for a custom VR headset, comprising both software and hardware components, is presented. The main contributions of this work are a customizable 3D-printable VR headset with two primary adjustment mechanisms, an extension to the MonoDio runtime to accommodate a new device driver with enabled tracking, and instructions for building both the hardware and software to construct a new device. The hardware and interactive design approach was used to tackle the problem step by step and gather learnings from it. In the final iteration, the headset houses a mechanism that allows adjustment of the distance between the lens and the display, and it allows adjustment of the IPD.

The main focus of this work was to create a base implementation on which other users can then modify and customize their headset with their hardware and software. To be clear, the goal was not to find a perfect solution to the problem, as this would greatly exceed the scope of this project. As discussed in section 4.6.4, the final headset, compared to others on the market, lacked some specifications. Although this might seem significant, at first, by being able to change the hardware of the headset, the potential peak performance can be significantly improved by providing, for example, a display with a higher resolution.

In section 5.2.7.2, two software side implementations are discussed. The clear difference between the OpenXR and the custom implementation is the compatibility range. OpenXR being compatible with SteamVR games and Unity already makes it usable with a lot of use cases that a custom implementation cannot implement. These promising results lead to the assumption that there can be many more applications used with the MonoDio. However, on the other hand, the custom method is much more flexible in terms of feature set, as the OpenXR project has a lot of complexity. Making the custom script a feasible solution for specialized use cases where compatibility with multiple software is not a requirement.

A problem that arose in the end of the MonoDio solution is that the views are rendered

in a window that does not split. Two approaches were evaluated, one where the content of the window is copied and displayed on each display in full screen, and the other where the window is moved over both screens. The latter method was evaluated to be superior because the latency that the first method added was not feasible.

Compared to other projects in this field, our solution proposes a much more flexible approach. With an eye module that can be swapped by screwing and unscrewing 5 screws per side, the lens-display configuration can be swapped out. This module also includes an adjustment mechanism for the display-to-lens distance to fine-tune it per person, making it potentially a better user experience. With an OpenXR implementation on the software side, which also integrates a swappable VI-SLAM interface with Windows and Linux support, certain openness to different VR applications is given, which would otherwise not be possible.

7.2 Future Work

Many different adaptations, implementations, tests, and improvements are left due to the lack of time. For hardware, future work would focus on the headset itself. One of the first things which are needed is a headstrap such that the user can mount the device to the face. This means extending a shell from the case with a cutout and cushioning for the user's face. This then allows for the straps to be secured and the headset to be used without needing to hold it. Furthermore, the IPD adjustment should accommodate a wider range, specifically in the lower range. This could be done by moving the display and the lenses closer to the center. Also, an integration of a mono display setup, meaning instead of using two displays, one large display is used where both views can be rendered on one screen, can be useful to support more hardware. This could be realized by fixing the screen in the middle of the case, with only the eye modules moving the lenses. The problem with only one display is that the display-to-lens distance can not be altered for only one eye.

Also, different premade parts would be a great addition. A library of components that can be 3D printed and assembled would greatly improve the ability to customize the headset. For example, we have already made lens brackets for different diameters or a range of display brackets for different kinds of screen. For tracking technologies, we do not need to limit them to a RealSense camera. Small RGB cameras can be integrated into the back compartment, making it feasible to create an RGB tracking system that does not need to be from a specific camera vendor.

This would also lead to an adaptation of the software, which would need adaptation in the retrieval of the camera images. Further work on the software part can be done by integrating a configuration file for the custom driver. There is already an implementation for loading variables from JSON, which can be utilized. This can improve the adjustability of the driver, which means that one does not need to recompile the program to change, for example, distortion parameters in order to adjust a new lens system.

Also, a suggestion would be to add a feature that splits up the two views into separate windows. This would lead to an optimal setup where each window can then be displayed in fullscreen. It would also deprecate the use of the workaround solutions of moving or copying the window itself. This could also be a big improvement in terms of setup.

Regarding the future of this project, the software will be open-sourced as a fork of Monado, and the CAD files will be uploaded to the same repository. Hopefully, some other people can then also contribute to this project and create a customized solution for themselves or others.

List of Acronyms

VR	Virtual Reality
AR	Augmented Reality
HMD	Head Mounted Display
XR	Extended Reality
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
FOV	field of view
OVR	Oculus VR
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping
VIO	Visual-Inertial Odometry
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
API	Application Programming Interface
PLA	Polylactic Acid
PETG	Polyethyleneterephthalat
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
IPD	Inter-Pupillary Distance
6DoF	6 Degrees of Freedom
PID	Product ID
VID	Vendor ID
DIB	Device Independent Bitmap
VDD	Virtual Display Driver
MSVC	Visual Studio 2022 compiler
FPS	Frames per Second
USB	Universal Serial Bus
RGB(-D)	Red, Green, Blue (plus Depth)

VI-SLAM	Visual-Inertial SLAM
VO	Visual Odometry

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